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Preliminary Characterization of Two Invasive Plant Species in Lebanon:
Ailanthus altissima MILL. and *Oxalis pes-caprae* L.

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I would like to dedicate my thesis to the spirit of my beloved grandfather and to my dear friend Mr. Nicolas El Roumi for his constant support and encouragement.

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ABSTRACT

Invasive plants species are considered as one of the most devastating ecological problems of the 21st Century. It is ranked second after habitat loss, as the greatest threat to biological diversity and ecosystem functions. The current study is focusing on two terrestrial invasive plant species in Lebanon: *Ailanthus altissima* MILL. and *Oxalis pes-caprae* L. mainly due to their persistence and widespread invasion in different regions. To better understand the factors involved in their invasion patterns, a survey was conducted between December 2015 and June 2016 serving as a preliminary characterization. Samples and plant measurements were collected from 10 sites for *A. altissima* MILL. and 13 sites for *O. pes-caprae* L. *Ailanthus* was sporadically found almost in all the Lebanese territories, where it appears to have a broader spectrum of invasiveness, being able to invade a large number of habitat types from anthropogenic to natural sites. Most sites were rich in young trees which shows increased invasive potential in the future in addition to the high germination rate shown during the germination tests. The survey shows the propagation of *O. pes-caprae* L., towards new areas and altitudes where it wasn't reported before, whereas field observations shows only a vegetative reproduction through the underground bulbs. The relatively high density and number of daughter bulbils shows a significant indicator of this plant to be potentially invasive, especially through human interventions. Field observations shows that *Oxalis* forms monospecific patches early spring affecting the structure and function of the whole herbaceous ecosystem later on. Our results show the potential for these species to significantly alter the functioning of ecosystems in Lebanon. A lack of significant measures to limit their impact is noticed, whereas further studies should be done in order to focus more on their actual and potential biological and economic impacts and the alternatives to halt their ecological consequences.

Keywords: Invasive plant species, *Ailanthus altissima* MILL., *Oxalis pes-caprae* L., Survey, Propagation, Distribution, Characterization.

RÉSUMÉ

La biodiversité au Liban ainsi que dans d'autres parties du monde a connu des transformations et des changements majeurs au cours des années. L'invasion par des espèces exotiques constitue une des principales menaces en matière de biodiversité des écosystèmes et pose une sérieuse menace à l'économie. Nous avons sélectionné deux espèces considérées comme invasives au Liban, *Ailanthus altissima* MILL. et *Oxalis pes-caprae* L. L'étude a été effectuée entre Décembre 2015 et Juin 2016 en vue de caractériser ces deux espèces envahissantes et de mieux comprendre les facteurs impliqués dans leur pouvoir invasif. Des données ont été recueillies à partir de dix sites pour *Ailanthus altissima* MILL. et de 13 sites pour *Oxalis pes-caprae* L., situés dans différentes zones géographiques au Liban. *A. altissima* se trouve presque dans tous les territoires libanais où l'espèce est capable d'envahir différents types d'habitats d'origine anthropique et naturel. La plupart des sites étudiés étaient riches en jeunes arbres montrant un potentiel envahissant élevé dans le futur ainsi que les tests de germination avec un taux de 99%. En ce qui concerne *Oxalis pes-caprae* L., l'étude montre que cette espèce a envahi de nouveaux territoires. L'observation sur le terrain montre que le principal mode de sa propagation est par reproduction végétative, d'où une teneur très élevée de biomasse sèche agissant comme un paquet de réserve nutritionnelle, qui va lancer les nouvelles pousses dans la prochaine saison favorable, formant tout d'abord des taches homogènes affectant la structure et la fonction de l'écosystème herbacé.

Nos résultats confirment le potentiel de ces espèces à modifier significativement le fonctionnement des écosystèmes au Liban alors que des études plus poussées semblent nécessaire afin d'étudier leur impact écologique et économique.

Mots-clés : Plantes envahissantes, *Ailanthus altissima* MILL., *Oxalis pes-caprae* L., Sondage, Propagation, Distribution, caractérisation.

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INTRODUCTION

Biological invasions can be defined as a multistage process that occurs when a species is transported from its native range to a novel region in which it is able to survive and reproduce, establish viable populations, and then spread widely (Richardson *et al.*, 2000). Consequently, understanding the effect of biological invasions and the factors supporting the invasion process is an important area of research that emerges as a new discipline and research area (Davis, 2003).

Lebanon is considered to be a true “hotspot” mainly due to its particular geographic location, mountainous topography and the great diversity in its climatic conditions (Lebanon’s National Biodiversity Strategy and Action Plan, 2016). One of the main threats to the Lebanese biodiversity is the invasion of alien species. More than fifty terrestrial invasive plant species have been identified in Lebanon and in the Middle East according to the Global Invasive Species Database website, Dafni and Heller, 1982; Haidar and Sabra, 2012 and Tohmé and Tohmé, 2007, 2014.

The lack of relevant studies, assessments and the complete absence of any preventative and protective measures in Lebanon are increasing the risk of plants invasion and their impacts (SOER, 2010).

Two terrestrial invasive plant species were selected for this study, one a woody plant and one is herbaceous: *Ailanthus altissima* MILL. (Tree of Heaven) and *Oxalis pes-caprae* L. (Bermuda buttercup) due to their persistence and widespread invasion in different geographical regions in Lebanon.

Ailanthus altissima (P. Miller) Swingle (*Simaroubaceae*) is a fast-growing deciduous tree 27–30 m high, native to China and North Vietnam but it is widely planted in the Mediterranean as an ornamental since the 18th century (Kowarik and Säumel, 2007). Based on the conducted survey and interacting with locals, it was probably first introduced during late Ottoman period as ornamental tree where it is currently invading most of the Lebanese territories. *Ailanthus* can establish by wind-dispersed seeds (samaras) and also by resprouts, by developing root networks that form dense clonal stands (Kowarik, 1995). In its introduced range, it is best known for its fast occupation of highly disturbed sites and capability of invading natural vegetation and especially

flood plain vegetation, rocky outcrops and other similarly open habitats (Hadjikyriakou and Hadjisterkotis, 2002; Call and Nilsen, 2003).

Oxalis pes-caprae L. (*Oxalidaceae*), native to the Cape Region of South Africa, is currently widespread throughout the Mediterranean Basin and North Africa (Rottenberg and Parker, 2004). Growing up to 30 cm in height, it rarely produces any seeds. Instead, it reproduces via the production of small (2 mm to 2 cm in diameter) underground bulbs spread up to 47 cm by subterranean contractile roots (Pütz, 1994). Dispersal often occurs by ploughing, adhesion to vehicle tires or livestock hooves, and any other means of soil movement such as earthworks and road construction (Gimeno *et al.*, 2006). According to literature reviews, Mouterde, 1966; Grigulis *et al.*, 2001; Lambrinos, 2002 and local nurseries, this agricultural invader was mainly introduced and spread to Lebanon through nurseries, deliberately as ornamental plant and accidentally in contaminated soil, latest 19th century from the Mediterranean region, mainly from Italy and Greece.

The main objective of the study was to assess a preliminary characterization of *Ailanthus altissima* MILL. (Tree of Heaven) and *Oxalis pes-caprae* L. (Bermuda buttercup) in Lebanon by understanding the introduction history of the two species, their biology, life cycle and distribution patterns and by establishing plots in different geographical regions and collecting data from these plots. These objectives were reached through the following activities:

- To assess on the geographical distribution and density of *Ailanthus altissima* MILL. and *Oxalis pes-caprae* L. in Lebanon.
- Characterize both the species in different geographical regions.
- Monitor growth stage of the two species in various seasons.
- Monitor and assess their reproductive patterns

The finding of this thesis will give insights for further studies on the two species in order to cover all factors that affect their invasion from genetic factors to their evolutionary biology and their impact on the ecosystem as well.

CHAPTER 1: LITERATURE REVIEW

1.1. Biological Invasion

Biological invasions comprise long-distance dispersal of organisms (or their propagules), followed by their successful establishment, rapid multiplication and range expansion (Richardson *et al.*, 2000). Those invasions usually have ecological and evolutionary consequences, both for the species and for the communities being invaded as well as for the invasive species themselves (Pysěk and Richardson, 2010). Consequently, it is essential to understand the on-going evolutionary processes during invasion and their contribution to the invasion success (Sakai *et al.*, 2001; Stockwell *et al.*, 2003). Each stage of the process is associated with barriers that a taxon must overcome to ultimately become invasive (Richardson *et al.*, 2000; Mitchell *et al.*, 2006). The first and possibly the most evident of these barriers is the geographical one, which is generally overcome through human assistance. Humans exchange thousands of species between different areas both intentionally and inadvertently (Nentwig, 2007); and while most introduced species become locally extinct soon after their arrival at the new region, a small part may establish and become invasive, frequently disrupting the structure and functioning of native communities (Mack *et al.*, 2000). Indeed, as a result of the intensification of human transport and commerce, invasion became a widespread phenomenon, including organisms of all taxonomic groups and affecting nearly all types of ecosystems and habitats (Pysěk *et al.*, 2008). Nevertheless, the role of humans in increasing the extent and frequency of biological invasions goes beyond purely acting as dispersal agents. For example, farming and horticulture are known to facilitate the establishment of nonindigenous species by protecting them from stochastic processes until they are capable of forming self-perpetuating populations, and are strongly linked with subsequent invasion events (Mack *et al.*, 2000). Additionally, human caused disturbances associated with agriculture and urban development can also play a major role in promoting the spread of alien species in the new areas (Kercher and Zedler, 2004).

1.1.1. Terrestrial Invasive Plant Species

Terrestrial Invasive plant species are plants that have the potential to thrive and spread outside their native habitat. According to Vermeij, 1996, Plant invasions can be defined as the appearance of a plant species and its geographical expansion in an area where it was not found previously. These plant species possess a diversity of characteristics enabling them to invade, adapt, persist and compete with crops and native vegetation (Westbrooks, 2001).

However, not all regions, biomes or habitats, are invaded to the same extent. It has been demonstrated that temperate regions are invaded more frequently than the tropics, new world more than the old world, islands more than the main lands and landscapes rich in native species more than landscapes poor in native species (Di Castri, 1990; Lonsdale, 1999; Kühn *et al.*, 2003; Rejmánek *et al.*, 2005; Daehler, 2006). In the same regions, the level of invasion usually varies strongly among habitats, suggesting that some habitats are more susceptible to invasions than others (Rejmánek *et al.*, 2005). According to Mack *et al.*, 2000, at a global scale, the transfer of invasive plant species through human agency is much more frequent and effective than through natural mechanism.

Invasive plants are considered as one of the most devastating ecological problems of the 21st Century. It is ranked second after habitat loss, as the greatest threat to biological diversity and ecosystem functions. These invasions are increasingly recognized for having important impacts on the structure, the function and the dynamics of different ecological and socio-economic systems (Brumback, 1998; Mack *et al.*, 2000).

The success and impact of alien species depends on their biology, on the environmental characteristics of the invaded ecosystem and on the biotic interactions with the receptive community (Vilà and Weiner, 2004).

Due to their impact on the environmental, ecological and socio-economic situations, the management of alien plants has become an important challenge and a high priority for the conservation of native species and natural habitats (Andreu and Vilà, 2011).

1.1.2. Problematic of Terrestrial Invasive Plant Species in Lebanon

According to “Lebanon’s National Biodiversity Strategy and Action Plan”, 2016, Lebanon, located at the far eastern end of the Mediterranean Sea, has a very rich and unique biodiversity mainly due to its biogeography, geology, ecology and historic human settlements (figure 1).

The biodiversity in Lebanon as well as in other parts of the world has known major transformations and changes, both positive and negative, throughout time. Main threats to Lebanon’s biodiversity have been identified from literature reviews and working sessions by various experts and stakeholders.

Figure 1: Lebanon in the heart of the Mediterranean Hotspot, www.cepf.net.

According to these experts, the main threats are:

- Habitat loss, fragmentation and destruction mainly due to urbanization.
- Unsustainable exploitation of natural resources.
- Agricultural land expansion.
- Pollution.
- Introduction of new improved varieties (agro-biodiversity).
- Climate change.
- Premeditated Fires.
- Overharvesting.
- Overgrazing.
- Lack of public awareness.
- And Invasive Alien Species.

According to Lebanon's 5th National Report to The Convention on Biological Diversity, most terrestrial invasive plant species have been introduced by human activity and now are propagating and spreading independently throughout the country. Invasive plant species (IPS) are considered one of the major threats to biodiversity in Lebanon. The lack of relevant studies and assessments is increasing the risk of their propagation and their impacts (SOER, 2010). According to the Global Invasive Species Database website, Dafni and Heller, 1982; Haidar and Sabra, 2012; Tohmé and Tohmé, 2007, 2014; more than 50 terrestrial invasive plant species are present in Lebanon and in the Middle East (Annex I).

Limited work is being conducted to identify, control and track the introduction of invasive species. No significant measures were taken in this purpose except in certain protected areas where the introduction of invasive species is forbidden by law, management plans are in place and they operate in respect to few invasive species threatening endemic species.

1.2. *Ailanthus altissima* MILL.

1.2.1. Origin and Distribution

Ailanthus altissima MILL. Swingle belongs to the *Ailanthus* genus, *Simaroubaceae* family, *Sapindales* order which comprises about 30 genera and 200 species. It's native to China and North Vietnam where it grows as a natural component of broadleaf forest (Hu, 1979). The name *Ailanthus* is derived from the native Moluccan name of *ailanto*, meaning sky tree or tree of heaven, referring to its height and rapid growth. It has many common names, including tree-of-heaven, heaven-wood, false varnish tree, Chinese sumac, paradise tree, copel tree, and stink tree (Davies, 1942).

Ailanthus has developed a secondary range on all other continents except Antarctica with a broad latitudinal range from the temperate to meridional zones as it shown in figure 2. Long and warm growing season are favorable conditions for growth, regular winter frost and annual precipitation of mostly >500 mm (Meloche and Murphy, 2006). In Lebanon, Tohmé and Tohmé, 2014, mentioned the presence of this species with no additional informations about its distribution.

Figure 2: Range of *Ailanthus altissima* MILL., with a differentiation of the native Chinese range (hatched; including possible early range expansions within China), and of the secondary world-wide distribution (black) (distribution data compiled and mapped by E. J. Jäger & E. Welk, AG Chorology, Institute for Biology Halle/Saale)

1.2.2. Morphological Characteristics

Ailanthus is a medium-sized deciduous tree which attains a maximum height of 27–30m in the temperate zone and 18–20m in the (sub-) meridional zone (Hunter, 2000; Arnaboldi *et al.*, 2002). It is characterized by smooth, pale grey bark and heavy foliage. It has large, odd-pinnately, pubescent or nearly glabrous, enlarged at the base and often tinged above. The leaflets are ovate-lanceolate with two to four glandular teeth at the rounded base (Hu, 1979). They may be arranged symmetrically or asymmetrically at the petiole (Troll, 1939). The terminal leaflet may have 1–2 enlarged lobes and may differentiate an additional single leaflet, pretending a ‘double’ terminal leaflet as shown in figure 3. Leaf size and number of leaflets are highly variable. It can grow as a single-stemmed tree with a broad crown and sometimes slightly drooping branches. It can also occur as groups of small stems from sprouting, often growing over 6 feet in a season. Some dieback of sprouts may occur in the winter but resprouting occurs (Feret, 1985). According to Miller, 1990, repeated freezing damage can lead to a reduction in seedling survival.

Figure 3: *Ailanthus altissima* MILL. leaf, photo by M. Abdallah, Ras Beirut, 22/5/2016.

The inflorescence type is racemose with a compound racemes. Flowers are mostly imperfect, but perfect flowers do occur (Feret, 1973). Both pistillate and staminate flowers are small, yellowish-green and arranged in large panicles at the ends of new shoots (Hu, 1979). The male flowers commonly produce three to four times as many flowers as the female plant, and is more conspicuous, particularly due to the odor staminate flowers emit as an attractant to insects. The flowers are usually regular, formed by a very small copular and lobed calyx, an annular and lobed gland, and five petals in the corolla that are pubescent on the inner surface (Davies, 1942; Hu, 1979). The ten stamens on the male flower are spreading with a globular anther and a glandular green disc. The female flower can be distinguished by the ten (or occasionally five) sterile stamens with heart shaped anthers as well as the five carpel pistil and star shaped stigma (Hu, 1979). Flowers do not open all at once. Seeds grew in fruit clusters with up to 500 samaras per cluster (figure 4).

The number of produced samaras increased exponentially with tree heights ranging from 0.4 to 8m, an 8-m-high tree produced approximately 650 fruit clusters with a total of 325,000 samaras. The root system of *Ailanthus* is shallow and spreading, and roots near the stem thicken into a storage structure. No true taproot occurs as most roots grow only in the upper 46 cm (18.1 inches) of the soil (Miller, 1990). This characteristic allows for high drought resistance, but causes difficulty surviving in areas of poor drainage, as is evidenced by its lack of occurrence in swamps and wetlands (Davies, 1942).

Figure 4: *Ailanthus altissima* MILL. inflorescence on the left, *Ailanthus altissima* MILL. samaras on the right, photo by M. Abdallah, Kehaleh, 26/5/2016.

1.2.3. Life Cycle and Biology

Ailanthus is a short-lived early successional tree that can attain a life span of > 100 years. By producing clonal offspring, the genetic individuals are nearly immortal. Sprouts from the first tree introduced in 1784 to America, for example, still exist today (Howard, 2004).

- **Germination and seedling establishment**

Information on germination rates varies broadly in literature. Direct sowing of seeds extracted from samaras in November yielded a germination rate of 98% at a constant temperature of 25 °C (Bory and Clair-Maczulajtys, 1980). Seeds collected in December germinated at rates of 86% and 83% in March and May, respectively, but only 64% germinated in September (Singh *et al.*, 1992). Little, 1974, reported a germination rate of 75% after 1 year of storage. Hildebrand, 2006, found 60% of seeds were still able to germinate after being stored for 2 years at room temperature.

Germination occurs without stratification but is enhanced by it. After a stay for 0, 4 and 12 days in humid sand, germination increased from 70% to 77% and 96%, respectively (Graves, 1990).

- **Seed banking**

Although *Ailanthus* does not form a long-term seed bank, it is able to establish temporary soil seed banks. Studies from deciduous forests in New York show it emerging from the seed bank at depth fractions of both 0–5 and 5–10 cm. Seedling number was not related to the importance values of adult trees (Kostel-Hughes *et al.*, 1998). Seeds remained viable on soil (Hildebrand, 2006) and in soil for at least 1 year (Hildebrand, 2006; Kota *et al.*, 2007).

- **Seedling establishment**

Germination occurs on bare soil as well as under leaf litter. Kostel-Hughes *et al.*, 2005, found no significant differences in the emergence of seedlings on bare soil and under leaf-litter layers of 1– 2 and 5 cm deep. Exposure of seeds to water for up to 10 days did not affect the stem increment of seedlings, which was however curbed when seeds stayed for 20 days in water (Kowarik and Säumel, 2007). By testing root and shoot development of seedlings under soil temperatures ranging from 15 to 31 °C, Heninger and White, 1974, found best growth at a soil temperature of 19 °C.

1.2.4. Reproduction

Ailanthus reproduces abundantly from both seed and root suckers from early life stages. On an urban site, seedlings (42.5%) and root suckers (57.5%) contributed to a total of 1912 excavated established 1-year-old individuals (Pan and Bassuk, 1986).

- **Sexual Reproduction**

Ailanthus reaches flowering maturity normally after 3–5 years. Early flowering can occur in 1-year-old saplings and root suckers. Flowers emerge in saplings 3 weeks after germination when saplings are exposed to long photoperiods and high light quantities. The flowers are morphologically abnormal and the developing seeds are not viable (Bory *et al.*, 1991). Feret, 1985, found early flowering 6 weeks after germination. Trees ranging from 12 to 20 years usually show the best seed production. *Ailanthus* is pollinated by honeybees, beetles and other nectar- and pollen-feeding insects (Miller, 1990).

- **Vegetative Regeneration**

Vegetative regeneration may originate from preexisting buds in the hypocotyl, adventitious buds on a cut section, axillary buds of cataphylls present at the base of the new shoots, and from roots as shown in figure 5.

Figure 5: Vegetative regeneration in *Ailanthus altissima* MILL. from (a) roots, (b) pre-existing buds in the hypocotyl, (c) adventitious buds on a cut section, (d) axillary buds of cataphylls present at the base of the new shoots, and (e) from stem fragments (a–d adapted from Bory *et al.*, 1991).

1.2.5. Dispersion

Dispersion occurred mainly by clonal growth, wind and water.

- **Clonal Growth**

By producing clonal offspring, the genetic individuals are nearly immortal and disperse themselves at the local scale. Howard, 2004, reported that root sprouts appear as far as 27 m from the parent stem. In southern France, Kowarik, 1995, observed clonal roadside populations up to a length of 120 m. Clonal growth starting on roadsides encroached into evergreen shrub communities out to a distance of 25 m, and arable fields up to 45 m. As clonal populations can be formed by more than one genetic individual, such distances should not necessarily be assigned to a single tree.

- **Wind**

Wind moves samaras both individually as well as aggregated in clusters descending from parts of the panicle. Morphologically, the centrally weighted, spirally twisted, winged samaras of *Ailanthus* are well adapted to wind dispersal. As samara morphology varies little within but largely among individuals, considerable variation in seed dispersal can be expected among trees (Bory and Clair-

Maczulajtys, 1980). Figure 6 illustrates the flight types that result from the capacity of samaras to rotate around both their longitudinal axis and their center of gravity, and also to fly without rotation.

Figure 6: Different types of transport of samaras of *Ailanthus altissima* MILL. (Bory and Clair-Maczulajtys, 1980).

- **Water**

Populations in river corridors as well as some anecdotal information suggest hydrochory as a secondary dispersal vector in *Ailanthus* (Parsons and Cuthbertson, 1992). This hypothesis finds experimental support: In a study by Kowarik and Säumel, 2007, 81% of exposed samaras were able to drift for at least 20 days on water. Both floating and submerged seeds were able to germinate after differing periods of exposure to water. In addition, 10% of buried stem fragments developed both adventitious shoots and roots after a stay of 3 or 10 days in water. Thus, moving water is believed to move sexual as well as asexual propagules over long distances.

- **Other dispersal vectors**

Rodents may occasionally act as dispersal agents by padding out their dens with collected samaras (Bory and Clair-Maczulajtys, 1980). In Texas, several bird species feed on *Ailanthus* seeds (Miller, 1990). Parsons and Cuthbertson, 1992, mention machinery moving seeds.

1.2.6. Response to Abiotic Factors

- **Temperature**

Ailanthus tolerates a broad amplitude of climatic conditions, but seasonal variation in temperature strongly affects survival, growth and spreading. As higher temperatures often coincide with drought stress, *Ailanthus* benefits from a reduced allocation to transpiring tissue coinciding with an enhanced relative growth rate of belowground biomass, an increased root elongation and a shift to fine and coarse roots within the root system. Increasing temperature also enhanced allelopathic effects, where “allelopathy” is a metabolite that provides competitive superiority, which has been identified as the major compound responsible for phytotoxic effects (Lawrence *et al.*, 1991).

- **Frost**

Cold injury varies with plant age. In early life stages, *Ailanthus* is most susceptible to frost. Frost injury to young plants as well as to the upper shoot parts of older plants can be related to a long growth period that coincides with a delayed hard frost. Miller, 1990, reported that late frost in spring induced the loss of all leaves, which was however compensated for in the same year.

- **Shade**

Ailanthus is classified as a shade-intolerant, early successional species with highly efficient photosynthesis on open sites (Marek, 1988). In contrast to shade-tolerant species, *Ailanthus* leaves that developed in shade had higher compensation points, lower rates of photosynthesis per unit area and lower relative rates of apparent photosynthesis in weak light (Bourdeau and Laverick, 1958). Consistently, seedlings were able to germinate, but not to establish new individuals under a closed forest canopy (Grime and Jeffrey, 1965; Kowarik, 1995; Knapp and Canham, 2000). Bory and Clair-Maczulajtys, 1980, found an enhanced height growth of cotyledons with increasing light intensities. The mean extension rate of saplings in gaps was about three times higher compared to forested areas (Kim, 1990). By colonizing open gaps, *Ailanthus* may reach the canopy faster than co-occurring native tree species and may then develop clonal ramets even in the shady sub-canopy (Knapp and Canham, 2000). At forest edges or in old-field succession, ramets may be found in shady conditions when other parts of the population receive full sunlight (Kowarik, 1995).

- **Soil**

Ailanthus grows on a broad range of natural and human-modified soils ranging from barren rocky substrates to sandy or clayey loams to calcareous dry and shallow soils and artificial depositions of gravel, sand and other materials, tolerating also saline and alkaline soils (Singh *et al.*, 1992). Growth is best on nutrient-rich, loamy soils, but *Ailanthus* also tolerates nutrient-poor soils (Miller,

1990). Consistently Pan and Bassuk 1986, found a better seedling growth in sandy loam compared to sand.

1.3. *Oxalis pes-caprae* L.

1.3.1. Origin and Distribution

Oxalis L. (Oxalidaceae) is a cosmopolitan genus of over 800 species, extremely variable in morphology and ecology, with two main centers of diversification, one in Central and South America and the other in southern Africa (Emshwiller and Doyle 1998).

Oxalis pes-caprae L., Bermuda buttercup, also known as sourgrass, soursop, African wood-sorrel and many other names, is a perennial bulbous geophyte native to South Africa, has become a persistent, troublesome and widespread invasive weed in several areas of the world (Vilà *et al.* 2006). More specifically, *O. pes-caprae* has spread widely across regions with a Mediterranean climate (similar to that of its native range), i.e., the Mediterranean basin, western and southern Australia, western South America and California; but has also been recorded in Pakistan, India, China, Japan, the South Island of New Zealand, and Florida (Lambdon, 2006). According to Mouterde, 1966; Grigulis *et al.*, 2001; Lambrinos, 2002 and local nurseries, *Oxalis pes-caprae*, L. was deliberately introduced to Lebanon through nurseries, as an ornamental plant and, accidentally in contaminated soil, during the early 19th century from other Mediterranean regions mainly from Italy and Greece.

Tohmé and Tohmé, 2014 mentioned the presence of three species from the *Oxalidaceae* family in Lebanon: “*Oxalis pes-caprae* L., *Oxalis corniculata* L., and *Oxalis articulata* Savigny”. The authors mentioned too that *Oxalis pes-caprae* L., is abundant up to 850 m altitude with its total absence in Beka’a valley.

1.3.2. Morphology

Oxalis pes-caprae L. is a perennial bulbiferous geophyte, growing up to 40 cm in height, with a true bulb. It sprouts at the apex of a vertical rhizome (Oberlander, 2009). With few modifications, *Oxalis* plant architecture conforms to the general vascular plant architecture as defined by internal structure as shown in figure 7 (Mauseth, 1988).

Figure 7: Morphological features of *Oxalis pes-caprae* L. (Marshall, 1987).

Oxalis leaves have a semi-amplexicaul bas region, a petiole and a lamina. They are divided into three heart-shaped leaflets, with a slightly hairy, often with a number of black specks surface (figure 8), petioles are up to 20 cm long (Vilà *et al.*, 2006).

Figure 8: *Oxalis pes-caprae* L. leaf, photo by M. Abdallah, Beblieh, 19/5/2016.

The bright, yellow flowers of *O. pes-caprae* open only if the sun is shining, are visited by foraging bees, but their short-style morph implies illegitimate pollination only (Rottenberg and Parker, 2004; Chapman, 2007). The heteromorphic flowers, grouped in cymose umbrellas, are pentamerous and pentacyclic, with five sepals, five petals fused at the base, ten stamens in two whorls of five and a gynoecium composed of five carpels with connate superior ovaries and distinct styles and stigmas (Castro *et al.*, 2013).

The introduced range of *Oxalis* is seedless and reproduces asexually from underground bulbs (Lane, 1984). *Oxalis pes-caprae* L. never has been known to bear fruit in the northern hemisphere (Rottenberg and Parker, 2004). The species blossoms during spring and a significant flowering mass is produced (Vilà *et al.*, 2006).

The bulb annually produces a contractile root, which pulls the bulb deeper each year, and bulbils are produced in the axillary buds of the vertical rhizome (Pütz, 1994). In Mediterranean ecosystems *Oxalis* bulbs remain dormant in the summer and sprout in the autumn (Vilà *et al.*, 2006). Upon sprouting, a short vertical underground shoot with lateral fine roots elongates from the parent bulb from which the rosette of leaves arise. At the base of the parent bulb a fleshy contractile root, as shown in figure 9, starts to develop after some leaves have emerged which later in the season serves as storage root tuber later, the contraction of the tuber elongated the ‘thread’ (the thin, rootless basal section of the shoot) to deeper soil horizons, which is thought to carry most new offspring bulbs (Chawdhry and Sagar, 1973; Pütz, 1994).

Figure 9: *Oxalis pes-caprae* L. root system, photo by M. Abdallah, Kehaleh, 21/4/2016.

Offspring bulbs may also arise from the shoot. Mature plants develop peduncles bearing flowers, although no viable seeds are produced in the invasive range. Peak vegetative growth followed by flowering occurs in winter, and plants completely senesce in spring (Vilà *et al.*, 2006). At the time of plant senescence, the tuber reserves are exhausted as offspring bulbs develop to final size (Verdaguer *et al.*, 2010; Castro *et al.*, 2013).

1.3.3. Reproductive and Vegetative Biology

Oxalis pes-caprae L. is heterostylous and self-incompatible (Ornduff, 1987). Sexual populations are either diploid or tetraploid, but a sterile, pentaploid race is believed derived from diploid X tetraploid hybrids. Although sexual plants can be weedy, the sterile pentaploid is apparently the only race that has become widespread outside of South Africa spreading entirely by bulblets

formed at the base of the succulent stem (Michael, 1965; Pütz, 1994; Peirce, 1997). Seeds of the diploid and tetraploid forms require a light stimulus for germination, which is enhanced by warm, moist conditions and require light (Peirce, 1997). The primary mode of reproduction, however, are bulbs produced by subterranean stems. Each bulb develops two different subterranean stem systems, one vertical and the other horizontal (Galil, 1968). The vertical stem gives rise to the aerial shoot system and may also produce axillary buds that develop into bulbs. The horizontal stem grows laterally by means of contractile roots. At maturity the horizontal stem becomes a storage organ (water, nutrients) and develops a terminal bulb immediately above the roots. Both kinds of stems can develop adventitious roots especially if damaged or cut by disturbance (e.g., plowing, digging). Mature plants may produce up to 20 bulblets, most of which are dispersed from the parent plant at the end growing season (Pütz, 1994). Bulbs are sensitive to freezing, but can persist for more than 3 years in a vegetative condition if kept dry (Galil, 1968). Cultivation and redistribution of soils are the most prevalent means of bulb dispersal, but birds and mole rats (in South Africa) also disperse the bulbs (Paspatis, 1985). Bermuda buttercup has been found to be toxic to livestock (Lane, 1984).

1.3.4. Invasion mechanism

The species' ability to spread vegetatively, assured by a profuse production of bulbs and a combination of shoot elongation and root contraction ability that distributes the bulbs along a distance of up to 47 cm, has been considered the major determinant of its success throughout the whole invasion process (Vilà and Gimeno, 2006).

In the past, the most important method of dispersal was the intentional propagation of the plant in gardens, from where it escaped to agricultural areas (Parsons and Cuthbertson, 2001). Currently, the species is no longer cultivated and long distance spread is mostly achieved through soil movement in agriculture and gardening (Parsons and Cuthbertson, 2001; Gimeno *et al.*, 2006).

Except for the above-mentioned factors, little is known about what makes *O. pes-caprae* such a successful invader. Therefore several unexplored issues could be involved with the success of this species, such as the release from natural enemies, the production of toxic compounds (e.g., oxalic acid characteristic of the genus) to which resident species have not yet evolved resistance, and particularly the high potential for rapid evolutionary changes already evident by the changes observed in its sexual system after invasion.

1.3.5. Impact

Invasion by *Oxalis* in the Mediterranean has been shown to decrease overall native plant diversity by about 10 %, especially with regard to annual grasses (Vilà *et al.*, 2006). However, this effect was lower than that measured for other invasive plant species. It is known that this species accumulate oxalic acid in its leaves, which is toxic to herbivore vertebrates if eaten in large quantities (Hulme, 2004). Oxalate is known to be a chelating agent for phosphorous, thus increasing its availability to other plants (Castro *et al.*, 2013). This raises the possibility that heavy

Oxalis invasion increases soil phosphorous availability due to the release of oxalic acid-rich litter. If so, spring pulses of phosphorous in *Oxalis*-invaded fields could enhance subsequent germination and growth of native species, thereby contributing to their maintenance (Vilà *et al.*, 2006).

1.4. Study Objectives

The general objective of this thesis was to better understand the factors involved in the invasion of two widely spread species in Lebanon: *Ailanthus altissima* MILL. and *Oxalis pes-caprae* L. For this purpose, a survey was conducted over the Lebanese terrain to assess their distribution, characterize in different geographical regions and monitor their growth stage in various seasons. After identifying the spread of the species, random plots were chosen and different parameters were taken in order to understand the species biology and its growth limiting factors.

CHAPTER 2: MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1. Survey and Sites Characterization

- *Ailanthus altissima* MILL.

A field survey was carried out in different areas of Lebanon from December 2015 to June 2016. A total of 22 locations, described in Annex II and III, were randomly chosen in order to determine the status of the studied species. Table 1 and 2 shows the characteristics of 10 chosen sites for *Ailanthus altissima* MILL. and of 13 chosen sites for *Oxalis pes-caprae* L. from where the data has been recorded

Table 1: Surveyed sites for *Ailanthus altissima* MILL.

Region name	Area	Altitude (m)	Latitude (° N)	Longitude (° E)
Beirut	Ras Beirut	36	33°53'58.67"	35°29'13.84"
	Kantari	63	33°53'44.19"	35°29'32.62"
	Corniche El Mazra'a	71	33°52'50.81"	35°29'47.01"
Mount Lebanon	Sahel Alma	74	34° 0'17.95"	35°38'59.92"
	Kehaleh	525	33°49'20.42"	35°35'18.21"
	Bekfaya	885	33°55'20.81"	35°41'19.05"
	Bhamdoun	1077	33°48'26.03"	35°39'24.49"
Beka'a Valley	Jdeita	961	33°48'58.70"	35°50'9.89"
North Lebanon	Chekka	11	34°20'21.46"	35°44'0.71"
South Lebanon	Tyre	11	33°16'14.19"	35°11'39.68"

Table 2: Surveyed sites for *Oxalis pes-caprae* L.

Region name	Area	Altitude (m)	Latitude (° N)	Longitude (° E)
Mount Lebanon	Ain El Remmeneh	18	33°51'36.23"	35°31'26.94"
	Gallery Sema'an	35	33°51'26.93"	35°31'34.72"
	Kehaleh	525	33°49'20.42"	35°35'18.21"
	Bet Chabeb	610	33°55'47.42"	35°40'0.42"
	Salima	820	33°52'25.51"	35°41'56.54"
	Zebdol	940	33°49'9.44"	35°50'50.44"
Beka'a Valley	Dhour El Abedyeh	977	33°48'42.28"	35°38'11.47"
South Lebanon	Beblieh	219	33°25'2.60"	35°19'38.86"
	Leba'a	370	33°33'3.44"	35°27'5.37"
Nabatieh	Nabatieh	427	33°23'12.52"	35°29'30.53"
	Borj El Mlouk	617	33°19'16.98"	35°33'52.41"
North Lebanon	Daher El Ein	105	34°23'41.90"	35°50'32.58"
	Qrain	690	34°23'33.61"	36° 2'17.80"

These sites were grasslands, roadsides, abundant fields and shrub lands. GPS locations and altitudes were recorded for each location where the species was detected and maps were generated for *Ailanthus altissima* MILL. (figure 10) and *Oxalis pes-caprae* L. (figure 11).

From *Ailanthus* sites, measurements were taken in a plot size of 20 m x 4 m. From *Oxalis* sites, using a (0.7 m x 0.7 m) metal square frame, 3 plots within each site were randomly chosen for data collection, with 0.5 m² per plot.

2.2. Equipment Used During Field Work

During the study the following equipment were used:

- Global Positioning System (GPS) instrument.
- Measuring tape.
- Metal square template size (0.7 m x 0.7 m).
- Camera.
- Paper bags for sampling.
- Trowel to collect soil samples.

Plant measurements were taken on the sites.

Figure 10: *Ailanthus altissima* MILL. sites, (tree symbol resemble to *Ailanthus altissima* MILL. populations).

Figure 11: *Oxalis pes-caprae* L. sites.

2.3. Plant Measurements

Ailanthus altissima MILL.

Within each sample plot (20 m x 4 m), we took in to consideration dead and alive specimens of *Ailanthus altissima* MILL. Alive trees were grouped into 3 categories based on their height, diameter at breast height and presence of inflorescence per tree:

- 1st category: Mother trees (an adult productive trees showing inflorescence).
- 2nd category: Juvenile trees (not in the reproductive phase).
- 3rd category: Saplings (individuals with less than 2 m in height).

For the 1st category, i.e. “Mother trees”, we measured 15 random trees: the height (m), Diameter at Breast Height (DBH) at 1.37 m (cm) and the number of inflorescence per tree were counted from ground level. Since the species is developing leaves before blooming and since this parameter is supposed to be a specific factor, therefore the number of leaves before the inflorescence, number of samaras per inflorescence were counted and the length of the main raceme (cm) on three

inflorescences per tree was measured. Those parameters were calculated on three trees out of 15 mother trees. The length (cm) and the maximum width (cm) of the leaf and the largest leaflet were measured on 3 leaves from 3 trees. The number of leaflets was counted too.

For the 2nd category, i.e. “Juvenile trees”, data on height (m), DBH at 1.37 m (cm) were collected from 15 random trees within this category. Of the 15 Juvenile trees, length (cm) and the maximum width (cm) of the leaf and the largest leaflet were measured from 3 leaves from 3 trees. The number of leaflets was counted too.

And for the 3rd category, “Saplings”, data on height (m), DBH at 10 % from the ground (cm), produced nodes per season, the length (cm) and the maximum width (cm) of the leaf and the largest leaflet were measured from 1 leaf from all (15) trees. The number of leaflets was counted too.

Using Dobbs allometric equation, specific for *Ailanthus altissima* MILL. Leaf Area Index (LAI), LAI was also calculated for the 3 categories: $LAI (m^2m^{-2}) = 17.8^{-27.0249} + 17.8 DBH^{-1.4109}$.

Leaf Area Index measures the amount of leaf material in an ecosystem, which requires data such as canopy light budgets, rainfall interception, evapotranspiration, surface temperature, reflectance or photosynthesis (McPehrson and Simpson, 2001).

***Oxalis pes-caprae* L.**

An olive orchard located in Beblieh (350 m), South Lebanon, was used as a starting point for monitoring this species.

Within each plot, species richness and the relative contribution of plant species were measured by counting the number all individual plants (*Oxalis* and other species), whereas density of *Oxalis* and other species were counted in the estimation of total species number per 1 m².

For *Oxalis*, the characteristics in the analysis include, measurements on leaves, petioles, peduncles, pedicels and bulbs were registered.

Leaves and petioles: the number of leaves was counted on 15 plants. The length of the longest leaf (cm) was measured on 3 leaves from 3 plants. Fresh and dry weight of leaves and petioles for 5 leaves from 5 plants were weighted.

Peduncles and pedicels: the number of peduncles was counted on 15 plants, the number of flowers per peduncle were also counted on 15 plants. The length of the longest peduncle (cm) was measured on 3 peduncles from 3 plants. Pedicels length (cm) was measured on 3 peduncles from 3 plants.

Bulbs: Bulbs were collected from a surface of 0.125 m^2 (1/4 of the metal square template) at 15 cm depth. Bulbs were divided into 3 groups based on their length (cm):

- 1st group: Bulbs with less than 0.7 cm.
- 2nd group: Bulbs between 0.7 and 1.2 cm
- 3rd group: Bulbs with more than 1.2 cm.

The number of bulbs within the 3 groups was counted, whereas density of *Oxalis* bulbs was estimated per 1 m^2 .

Fresh and dry weight of 15 individuals of bulbs with more than 1.2 cm were weighted in order to estimate the maximum vegetative growth in different sites.

2.4. Soil Samples and Measurements

From each chosen site, soil samples at 20 cm depth were collected for laboratory analysis at the soil analytical laboratory at the Faculty of Agricultural Sciences and Veterinary Medicine, Lebanese University, Dekweneh.

Each sample was cleaned by hand from plant debris and gravel. Soil agglomerates were also crushed by hand. Soil samples were air dried at room temperature for 72 hours then sieved and an analysis of the soil's texture and pH was made.

2.5. Climatic Data

There was no meteorological station at any of the chosen sites. The nearest meteorological station of the Lebanese Agricultural Research Institute was applied as the nearest equivalent.

The following table shows the mean monthly minimum and maximum temperatures and the precipitation index from December 2015 to June 2016

Table 3: Mean of monthly minimum and maximum temperature (°C) and the average precipitation (mm).

Month	Region														
	Beirut			Mount Lebanon			Beka'a Valley			South Lebanon			North Lebanon		
	Min	Max	mm	Min	Max	mm	Min	Max	mm	Min	Max	mm	Min	Max	mm
December 2015	11.9°	20.8°	82.8	7.8°	21.7°	82.4	-6.8°	18.2°	26.8	1.4°	23.1°	45.8	0.9°	21°	49.6
January 2016	9.95°	17.7°	257.4	3.5°	23.5°	285.6	-9.4°	18.2°	90.8	1.8°	23.7°	162	-3.8°	21.2°	280
February 2016	13.3°	22°	326.8	8.3°	28.6°	368.4	-2.5°	23.3°	109.6	3.7°	26.5°	241.8	4.4°	27.8°	364
March 2016	14.3°	24.2°	342.8	9.6°	32.1°	457.6	-0.4°	23.7°	162	0°	31.1°	271.6	7.4°	29.9°	466
April 2016	16.7°	31.1°	416	11.7°	33.2°	522.8	0°	30.4°	188	6.8°	31.7°	491.8	0°	28.2°	272.4
May 2016	18.2°	32°	448.2	15.1°	38.9°	555.2	0°	33.4°	234.2	12.9°	37.3°	537.8	14.1°	33.4°	275
Average	14.1°	24.6°	374.8	9.3°	30°	454.4	-3.2°	24.5°	162.28	3.5°	27.2°	350.16	4.7°	28.1°	341.4

2.6. Germination Test

A direct-seeding germination test was conducted at home 2 times at different timing. Seeds of *Ailanthus altissima* MILL. were collected, to determine its maximum germination potential, in December 2015 and in May 2016 (old seeds from 2015) from 4 different locations in Lebanon (Ras Beirut, Dekweneh, Kehaleh, Jounieh). After collection, seeds were weighted and stored in a dry closed plastic bags. The first seed germination experiments started in 17 April 2016 and the 2nd in 17 May 2016, both tests started by placing 100 seeds in 20-cm-height Styrofoam boxes containing moist, warm soil. Seed boxes were placed in a warm, sunny place. The examinations of the germination test were with 4 replications whereas a seed was considered to have germinated when the epicotyl elongated to 2 mm from the seed coat Measurement of maximum and minimum temperature was monitored on a daily basis.

2.7. Statistical Analysis

Statistical analysis (Mean, Standard deviation and Standard Error) were performed using Excel 2013 software package.

CHAPTER 3: RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1. *Ailanthus altissima* MILL.

3.1.1. Introduction and distribution of *Ailanthus altissima* MILL. in Lebanon

Based on the survey on the distribution and spread coupled with available literature and local knowledge, *Ailanthus altissima* MILL. could have been introduced to Lebanon as an ornamental tree during the Ottoman period (figure 12).

Figure 12: *Ailanthus altissima* MILL. tree in Mount Lebanon, late the 19th century, 1887, www.almashriq.hiof.no.

Later, after World War I, and during the French mediate period, *Ailanthus* was planted to provide shade as well as for camouflaging on train rails (figure 13).

Figure 13: Chekka Train rail before and after *Ailanthus altissima* MILL. invasion.
(A: Chekka train rail before *Ailanthus altissima* MILL. invasion, 1911, www.almashriq.hiof.no)
(B: Chekka train rail after *Ailanthus altissima* MILL. invasion, photo by M.Abdallah, 1/6/2016).

The tree was planted (used) for ornamental purposes as it quickly sprouts and takes less maintenance than other species, the purpose shifted later to become more of a production tree, specifically as a forage tree for honey bees.

Nowadays, this invasive species is spread over the Lebanese territories starting from the coastal strip (Tyre, Saida, Beirut, Jounieh, Jbeil, Chekka) up to the high mountains in Tannourine El Tahta, Mayrouba, Bhamdoun and ends up almost in the Beka'a valley, specifically in the central and northern parts of it (figure 14).

Figure 14: *Ailanthus altissima* MILL. distribution in Lebanon (highlighted in red).

Ailanthus altissima MILL. is also known in Lebanon under many names such as: شجرة الله، شجرة السرطان "السما، شجرة الخردل و شجرة السرطان".

3.1.2. Life Cycle

The monitoring of the biological cycle of *Ailanthus altissima* MILL over the Lebanese coast since November 2015 showed behavior alternation as it began shedding leaves and changing its morphology into a leafless tree as shown in figure 15.

Figure 15: Leafless *Ailanthus altissima* MILL. tree, photo by M. Abdallah, Tyre, 25/11/2015.

Based on the 2015-2016 assessment, the dormancy period extends from November till the first week of March, sprouting starts from the 1^{rst} week of March. Flowering period on mother trees starts 2 weeks after sprouting.

3.1.3. Density

The assessment of *Ailanthus altissima* MILL. density from 10 chosen sites. Density of dead, mother, juvenile trees and saplings were estimated in 1 ha (table 4). (The order of the regions in the table below is based on the altitude from low to high).

Table 4: *Ailanthus altissima* MILL. density parameters.

	Dead trees	Mother trees	Juvenile trees	Saplings	Total trees
Tyre	0	125	11375	19000	30500
Chekka	0	250	7125	19125	27625
Ras Beirut	125	375	8500	19750	28750
Kantari	0	2000	3375	6625	12000
Cornich El Mazra'a	0	2000	7875	18125	28000
Sahel Alma	0	1250	11625	17375	28875
Kehaleh	1500	1250	8250	17625	28625
Bekfaya	250	2250	8250	15500	26250
Jdeita	1375	5875	9000	12500	28500
Bhamdoun	1000	3375	8125	11125	23625

Density of dead adult trees was the lowest with 0 tree in Tyre, Chekka, Kantari, Corniche El Mazra'a and Sahel Alma and the highest with 1500 trees in Kehaleh.

Density of mother trees was the lowest with 125 trees in Tyre and the highest with 5875 trees in Jdeita.

Density of juvenile trees was the lowest with 7125 trees in Chekka and the highest with 11625 trees in Sahel Alma.

Density of saplings was the lowest with 11125 trees in Bhamdoun and the highest with 28750 trees in Ras Beirut.

Density of total trees was the lowest with 12000 trees in Kantari and the highest with 28875 trees in Sahel Alma. 12000.

Over all the 10 sites, the studied plots shows an average of 26250 individuals per ha, in which, dead trees count for 2% of total number of trees and alive trees forms 98%. Whereas within alive trees, mother trees forms 7% of the population, juvenile trees 32% and saplings 61%.

The sites rich in young trees show theoretically high invasive potential due to the high density of future mother trees.

However the high germination rate as shown during our experiments is giving in situ a high density of young trees. Consequently they will be subject to a high competition pressure reducing later the number of adult trees. This is reflecting such a natural balance that control or reduce the percentage of adult mother trees in the sites. Further studies could confirm the effect of this ration on the invasion potential. Maybe the species is self-toxic. That is why on some sites such as in Kahale we are noticing a transition of the sites.

3.1.4. Mother Trees Growth

Table number 5 shows the morphological characteristics of *Ailanthus altissima* MILL. mother trees in 5 specific sites out of 10 as the remaining sites do not have enough individuals to be included in the statistical analysis.

Table 5: Morphological characteristics of *Ailanthus altissima* MILL. mother trees.

	Kantari			Cornich El Mazra'a			Bekfaya			Jdeita			Bhamdoun		
	Mean ± SE	Min	Max	Mean ± SE	Min	Max	Mean ± SE	Min	Max	Mean ± SE	Min	Max	Mean ± SE	Min	Max
Height (m)	13.1 ± 1.8	6	28	17.2 ± 1.3	9	25	10.2 ± 0.8	6	17	6.6 ± 0.4	4	9	6.8 ± 0.4	4.5	9
DBH (cm)	14.2 ± 2.7	6.1	44.5	13.7 ± 1.2	6.1	24.8	12.1 ± 1.6	6.1	23.8	10.2 ± 1.9	4.7	26.1	10.6 ± 1.8	5.1	26.7
Inflorescence															
Number of leaves before inflorescence	10 ± 0.4	9	13	9 ± 0	9	9	9 ± 0	9	9	5.6 ± 0.2	4	6	5.6 ± 0.2	4	6
Number of inflorescences	56 ± 8.5	18	102	72 ± 12	3	120	40 ± 7.2	12	85	40 ± 7.2	12	85	40 ± 7.2	12	85
Number of samaras per inflorescence	845 ± 131	472	1400	744 ± 154	404	1860	474 ± 67.6	230	920	561 ± 67.5	404	1160	563 ± 67.5	416	1080
Length of the main raceme (cm)	23 ± 1.2	19	20	20 ± 1	16	24	20 ± 0.7	14	27	20 ± 1.2	15	26	17 ± 0.7	14	21
Leaf															
Length (cm)	46.7 ± 2.6	35	58	49.7 ± 1.3	35	71	47.5 ± 1.6	43	57	49.7 ± 1.6	35	71	49.3 ± 2	44	58
Max. Width (cm)	25 ± 1.2	18	30	25.5 ± 1.2	21	30	25.3 ± 0.9	21	28	23.1 ± 0.9	15	31	23.1 ± 5.1	22	30
Number of leaflets	18.5 ± 0.8	15	23	16.2 ± 0.9	12	20	17.8 ± 0.8	16	22	19 ± 0.8	14	25	18.4 ± 0.7	16	22
Largest leaflet															
Length (cm)	11.8 ± 0.5	9	15	13.1 ± 0.6	11	16	12.4 ± 0.3	11	14	10.6 ± 0.3	6.5	14	11.8 ± 0.2	11	13
Width (cm)	4.5 ± 0.2	3.5	5.6	5.1 ± 0.2	4	6	5 ± 0.1	4	5.5	4.5 ± 0.1	3	6.5	4.7 ± 0.2	3.5	5.5

SE: Standard Error / Min: Minimum /Max: Maximum

Height (m), DBH (Diameter at Breast Height) (cm) and the number of inflorescence were estimated for 15 trees.

Number of leaves before the inflorescence, number of samaras per inflorescence, length of the initial node (cm) on 3 inflorescences per tree over 15 trees were counted.

Length (cm) and maximum width (cm) of the leaf and the largest leaflet were measured on 3 leaves from 3 trees.

- **Height**

Mother trees height ranges from 6.6 ± 0.4 m in Jdeita to 17.2 ± 1.3 m in Corniche El Mazra'a with a minimum of 4 m in Jdeita and a maximum of 28 m in Kantari.

The tallest tree is present in a cemetery in Tyre; it has nearly 110 years, with height of 28 m and a stem diameter of 1.72 m, this tree is divided into 7 large trunks with a circumference ranging from 0.23 m to 0.47 m (figure 16). Similarly, Kowarik and Säumel, 2007, reported that the tallest tree known grew up in a park near Bonn, Germany; at the age of 130 years, it had a height and a stem diameter of 1.27 m.

- **Diametre at Breast Height (DBH)**

It ranges from 10.1 ± 1.9 cm in Jdeita to 14.2 ± 2.7 cm in Kantari with a minimum of 4.7 cm observed in Jdeita, and a maximum of 44.5 cm observed in Kantari. We are much less than the records of 1.27 m in Germany.

- **Inflorescence**

Number of leaves before inflorescence ranges from 5.6 ± 0.2 in Bhamdoun to 10 ± 0.4 in Kantari with minimum of 4 observed in Bhamdoun and a maximum of 13 observed in Kantari. Consequently this factor unexpectedly was varying from site to site, further studies could clarify the relationship.

Number of inflorescence per tree ranges from 40 ± 7.2 in Bekfaya, Jdeita and Bhamdoun to 72 ± 12 in Corniche El Mazra'a with a minimum of 3 and a maximum of 120 observed in Corniche El Mazra'a.

Number of samaras per inflorescence ranges from 561 ± 67.5 in Jdeita to 845 ± 131 in Kantari with a minimum of 230 flowers per inflorescence observed in Bekfaya, and a maximum of 1860 observed in Corniche El Mazra'a. An 18-m-high tree produced approximately 120 fruit clusters with a total of 223,200 samaras

In a study by Kowarik and Säumel, 2007, the number of produced samaras increased exponentially with tree heights ranging from 0.4 to 8 m, an 8-m-high tree produced approximately 650 fruit clusters with a total of 325,000 samaras.

Concerning length of the main raceme, in the racemose inflorescence, it ranges from 17 ± 0.7 cm in Bhamdoun to 23 ± 1.2 cm in Kantari with minimum of 14 cm observed in Bekfaya and Bhamadoun and a maximum of 27 cm observed in Bekfaya.

- **Leaf**

The length of the compound pinnate leaves ranges from 46.7 ± 2.6 cm in Kantari to 49.7 ± 1.6 cm in Jdeita with a minimum of 35 cm in Kantari, Corniche El Mazra'a and Jdeita and a maximum of 71 cm in Jdeita and Corniche El Mazra'a.

The maximum width ranges from 23.1 ± 0.9 cm in Jdeita to 25.5 ± 1.2 cm in Corniche El Mazra'a with a minimum of 15 cm and a maximum of 31 cm in Jdeita.

The number of leaflets varies within the sites with a range from 16.2 ± 0.9 in Corniche El Mazra'a to 19 ± 0.8 in Jdeita with a minimum of 12 leaflets observed in Corniche El Mazra'a and a maximum of 25 in Jdeita.

- **Largest leaflet**

The length of the largest leaflet ranges from 10.6 ± 0.3 cm in Jdeita to 13.1 ± 0.6 cm in Corniche El Mazra'a with a minimum of 6.5 cm in Jdeita, and a maximum of 16 cm in Corniche El Mazra'a.

From 4.5 ± 0.1 cm in Jdieta to 5.1 ± 0.2 cm in Corniche El Mazra'a ranges the width of the largest leaflet, with a minimum of 3 cm in Jdeita and a maximum of 6.5 cm in Jdeita.

Leaf size and number of leaflets are highly variable. Most authors reported maximum leaf lengths between 0.6 and 1.0 m (Hunter, 2000). The largest leaf known thus far is from a repeatedly cut plant from an urban site in Berlin, which produced a 3.0-m current-year shoot. The leaf had a length of 1.67 m, a maximum width of 0.46 m with 43 leaflets (Kowarik and Säümel, 2007).

The relatively wide compound leaves is making its shade effect high so the impact on the local herbaceous layer is heavy that is increasing its elimination impact or pressure.

3.1.5. Juvenile Trees Growth

Table number 6 below shows the morphological characteristics of the *Ailanthus altissima* MILL. juvenile trees in 10 chosen sites (the order in the table below is based on the region altitude from low to high).

Table 6: Morphological characteristics of *Ailanthus altissima* MILL. juvenile trees.

	Tyre			Chekka			Ras Beirut			Kantari			Cornich El Mazra'a		
	Mean ± SE	Min	Max	Mean ± SE	Min	Max	Mean ± SE	Min	Max	Mean ± SE	Min	Max	Mean ± SE	Min	Max
Height (m)	3.1 ± 0.1	2.1	4.2	3.7 ± 0.2	2	6	8.9 ± 0.8	4	14	3.5 ± 0.3	2	6	4.9 ± 0.4	3	7
DBH (cm)	1.06 ± 0.2	2.1	5.4	4.6 ± 0.5	1.5	8.6	5.3 ± 0.3	2.5	7.3	5 ± 0.7	1.2	9.5	5.3 ± 0.4	3.1	9.8
Leaf															
Length (cm)	69 ± 2.1	55	78	125.7 ± 2.8	112	144	94.6 ± 2.4	86	110	98.6 ± 1.9	92	107	108 ± 8.7	69	144
Max. width (cm)	36.1 ± 0.6	34	40	37.7 ± 2.2	27	47	37.7 ± 2.1	31	50	36.5 ± 0.8	33	41	35.4 ± 3.1	27	46
Number of leaflets	22 ± 1.4	20	24	31 ± 0.9	28	36	25 ± 1.1	19	29	31 ± 0.5	29	34	26 ± 1.8	17	32
Largest leaflet															
Length (cm)	17.6 ± 0.2	16	19	19.05 ± 0.8	14	17	19.2 ± 0.9	16	25	17.5 ± 0.3	15	19	18.3 ± 0.8	16	23
Width (cm)	7.2 ± 0.1	7	8	7.1 ± 0.2	6	8	7.8 ± 0.5	6	12	7.1 ± 0.3	6	8.5	6.7 ± 0.2	5.5	8

	Sahel Alma			Kehaleh			Bekfaya			Jdeita			Bhmadoun			
	Mean ± SE	Min	Max	Mean ± SE	Min	Max	Mean ± SE	Min	Max	Mean ± SE	Min	Max	Mean ± SE	Min	Max	
Height (m)	8.9 ± 0.8	4	14	4 ± 0.4	2.2	8	4.1 ± 0.3	2	7	3.1 ± 0.1	2.2	5	2.9 ± 0.2	2	4	
DBH (cm)	5.3 ± 0.3	2.5	7.3	4.6 ± 0.4	2.5	8.5	4.1 ± 0.4	1.7	7	1.9 ± 0.1	1.2	2.5	1.9 ± 0.1	1.2	2.7	
Leaf																
Length (cm)	85.4 ± 4.7	61	102	105.1 ± 3.9	90	123	86.7 ± 3.3	74	105	71.7 ± 3.2	61	79	71.3 ± 2.08	57	84	
Max. width (cm)	39 ± 2.4	29	47	34.2 ± 0.8	31	37	33.1 ± 0.8	31	37	31.1 ± 1.1	26	35	30.4 ± 1.1	26	35	
Number of leaflets	26 ± 1.01	19	30	29 ± 1.03	26	35	24 ± 1.4	19	29	22 ± 0.8	14	25	22 ± 0.8	14	25	
Largest leaflet																
Length (cm)	19.3 ± 1.4	12.5	17	16.7 ± 0.3	15	18	15.7 ± 0.4	14	17	15.7 ± 0.5	14	17	15.1 ± 0.5	12.5	19	
Width (cm)	6.5 ± 0.4	4.5	8	5.8 ± 0.2	5	7	5.9 ± 0.1	5	6	5.6 ± 0.1	5	7	5.3 ± 0.1	5	6	

SE: Standard Error / Min: Minimum /Max: Maximum

Height (m), DBH (Diameter at Breast Height) (cm) were measured for 15 trees.

Length (cm) and maximum width (cm) of the leaf and the largest leaflet were measured on 3 leaves from 3 trees.

- **Height**

Juvenile trees height ranges from 2.9 ± 0.2 m in Bhamdoun to 8.9 ± 0.8 m in Sahel Alma and Ras Beirut with a minimum of 2 m in Bhamdoun and a maximum of 14 m in Ras Beirut and Sahel Alma. We should take into consideration the shade and the density effect of etiolation in plants making juvenile trees higher whenever high density is reported.

- **Diameter at Breast Height (DBH)**

Juvenile trees diameter average ranges from 1.9 ± 0.1 cm in Bhamdoun to 5.3 ± 0.4 cm in in Corniche El Mazra'a with minimum of 1.2 cm observed in Jdeita and Bhamdoun and a maximum of 9.8 cm observed in Corniche El Mazra'a.

- **Leaf**

The length of the leaf ranges from 69 ± 2.1 cm in Tyre to 125.7 ± 2.8 cm in Chekka with a minimum of 55 cm observed in Tyre and a maximum of 144 cm observed in Chekka and Corniche El Mazra'a.

The max width ranges from 30.4 ± 1.1 cm in Bhamdoun to 39 ± 2.4 cm in Sahel Alma with a minimum of 26 cm in Bhamdoun and Jdeita, and a maximum of 50 cm in Ras Beirut.

The number of leaflets varies within the sites from 22 ± 0.8 in Bhamdoun to 31 ± 0.5 in Chekka with a minimum of 14 in Bhamdoun and a maximum of 36 leaflets observed in Chekka.

Here we notice that the leaf area is higher in juvenile trees since it is a vital growth factor while in adult trees the higher number of leaves is compensating a reduced leaf size. More over adult trees have other reproductive priorities.

- **Largest leaflet**

The length of the biggest leaflet ranges from 15.1 ± 0.5 cm in Bhamdoun to 19.3 ± 1.4 cm in Sahel Alma with a minimum of 12.5 cm in Bhamdoun, and a maximum of 25 cm in Ras Beirut.

From 5.3 ± 0.5 cm in Bhamdoun to 7.8 ± 0.1 cm in Ras Beirut ranges the width of the largest leaflet, with a minimum of 4.5 cm in Sahel Alma and a maximum of 12 cm in Ras Beirut.

3.1.6. Saplings Growth

Table number 7 shows the morphological characteristics of *Ailanthus altissima* MILL. saplings in 10 chosen sites (the order in the table below is based on the region altitude from low to high).

Table 7: Morphological characteristics of *Ailanthus altissima* MILL. saplings.

	Tyre			Chekka			Ras Beirut			Kantari			Cornich El Mazra'a		
	Mean ± SE	Min	Max	Mean ± SE	Min	Max	Mean ± SE	Min	Max	Mean ± SE	Min	Max	Mean ± SE	Min	Max
Height (m)	0.8 ± 0.07	0.42	1.45	0.8 ± 0.09	0.3	1.5	0.8 ± 0.09	0.37	1.5	0.8 ± 0.09	0.3	1.35	0.8 ± 0.08	0.5	1.5
DBH (cm)	1.9 ± 0.1	1.2	3	1.2 ± 0.2	0.1	3	1.1 ± 0.15	0.4	2.2	1.1 ± 0.1	0.4	1.9	0.7 ± 0.1	0.1	1.4
Number of nodes	19 ± 0.9	12	24	19 ± 1.3	12	32	14 ± 0.9	8	20	18 ± 1.9	8	32	20 ± 1.8	7	35
Leaf															
Length (cm)	42.6 ± 2.6	29	65	38.5 ± 3.5	21	64	54.2 ± 5.5	33	91	41.1 ± 4.1	19	65	38.1 ± 3.1	18	64
Max. width (cm)	26.3 ± 1.1	20	34	22.8 ± 1.3	14	34	28.1 ± 1.9	20	43	22.6 ± 0.6	17	26	20.5 ± 1.3	11	34
Number of leaflets	19 ± 0.9	12	28	17 ± 1.1	9	25	17 ± 1	13	27	18 ± 1.4	9	25	15 ± 0.7	11	21
Largest leaflet															
Length (cm)	12.7 ± 0.6	10	16	11.6 ± 0.6	7	16	14.4 ± 1.01	10	23	11.9 ± 0.3	10	14	10.3 ± 0.6	5.5	16
Width (cm)	4.1 ± 0.1	3	5	4.1 ± 0.3	2	7	5.4 ± 0.3	3	8	4.03 ± 0.2	2	6	3.8 ± 0.3	2.5	7

	Sahel Alma			Kehaleh			Bekfaya			Jdeita			Bhamdoun		
	Mean ± SE	Min	Max	Mean ± SE	Min	Max	Mean ± SE	Min	Max	Mean ± SE	Min	Max	Mean ± SE	Min	Max
Height (m)	0.8 ± 0.1	0.26	1.5	0.8 ± 0.08	0.36	1.43	1.1 ± 0.1	0.56	1.61	0.8 ± 0.09	0.36	1.43	0.8 ± 0.09	0.36	1.43
DBH (cm)	0.8 ± 0.1	0.1	2.2	1.8 ± 0.1	0.9	2.8	1.1 ± 0.1	0.4	2.4	1.1 ± 0.1	0.1	2.4	1.1 ± 0.1	0.1	2.4
Number of nodes	22 ± 1.8	8	34	21 ± 1.4	14	38	22 ± 1.6	13	35	21 ± 1.7	7	35	19 ± 1.9	7	35
Leaf															
Length (cm)	36.7 ± 5.6	11	84	43.6 ± 3.8	19	68	45.6 ± 3.8	20	68	41.7 ± 3.8	18	68	41.9 ± 3.5	18	68
Max. width (cm)	20.2 ± 2.4	9	43	23.3 ± 1.1	17	34	24.1 ± 1.1	18	34	21.2 ± 1.3	10	34	21.1 ± 1.6	10	34
Number of leaflets	16 ± 0.9	9	21	17 ± 1	9	25	17 ± 0.8	11	21	17 ± 0.6	11	21	16 ± 0.9	11	21
Largest leaflet															
Length (cm)	10.3 ± 1.3	5	23	12.1 ± 0.5	9.5	17	12.1 ± 0.5	10	17	10.9 ± 0.6	5.5	17	10.9 ± 0.6	5.5	17
Width (cm)	3.7 ± 0.4	2	8	4.4 ± 0.2	2.5	6	4.4 ± 0.2	2.5	6	4 ± 0.2	2.5	6	4 ± 0.2	2.5	6

SE: Standard Error / Min: Minimum /Max: Maximum

Height (m), DBH (Diameter at Breast Height at 10 % from the ground) (cm) and number of nodes were measured for 15 trees.

Length (cm) and maximum width (cm) of the leaf and the largest leaflet were measured from 1 leaf from all (15) tre

- **Height**

Saplings height average ranges from 0.8 ± 0.07 cm in Tyre to 1.1 ± 0.1 cm in Bekfaya with a minimum of 0.26 cm observed in Sahel Alma and a maximum of 1.61 cm observed in Bekfaya.

- **Diametre at Breast Height (DBH)**

Circumference ranges from 2.3 ± 0.3 cm in Corniche El Mazra'a to 6.05 ± 0.3 cm in Tyre with a minimum of 0.4 cm observed in Chekka, Sahel Alma and Corniche El Mazra'a and a maximum of 9.5 cm observed in Tyre and Chekka.

- **Number of nodes**

The number of produced nodes per season ranges from 14 ± 0.9 in Ras Beirut to 22 ± 1.8 in Sahel Alma with a minimum of 7 nodes in Corniche El Mazra'a, Jdeita and Bhamdoun and a maximum of 38 nodes in Kehaleh.

- **Leaf**

The length of the leaf ranges from 36.7 ± 5.6 cm in Sahel Alma to 54.2 ± 5.5 cm in Ras Beirut with a minimum of 11 cm observed in Sahel Alma and a maximum of 91 cm observed in Ras Beirut.

The width ranges from 20.2 ± 2.4 cm in Sahel Alma to 28.1 ± 1.9 cm in Ras Beirut with a minimum of 9 cm observed in Sahel Alma and a maximum of 43 cm observed in Sahel Alma and Ras Beirut.

The number of leaflets varies within the sites with a range from 15 ± 0.7 in Corniche El Mazra'a to 19 ± 0.9 in Tyre with a minimum of 9 leaflets observed in Chekka, Kantari, Sahel Alma and Kehaleh and a maximum of 28 leaflets observed in Tyre.

- **Largest leaflet**

The length of the biggest leaflet ranges from 10.3 ± 0.6 cm in Corniche El Mazra'a to 14.4 ± 1.01 cm in Ras Beirut with a minimum of 5 cm observed in Sahel Alma and a maximum of 23 cm observed in Sahel Alma and Ras Beirut.

From 3.7 ± 0.4 cm in Sahel Alma to 5.4 ± 0.3 cm in Ras Beirut ranges the width of the biggest leaflet, with a minimum of 2 cm observed in Sahel Alma, Chekka and Kantari, and a maximum of 8 cm observed in Sahel Alma and Ras Beirut.

We have to add a comparative table or paragraph to show how leaf area or leaf size is evolving from young to juvenile to adult.

3.1.7. Leaf Area Index

Table number 8 shows the Leaf Area Index (m^2m^{-2}) for the 3 categories from 10 sites (LAI for mother trees in 5 specific sites out of 10 as the remaining sites do not have enough individuals to be included in the statistical analysis).

Table 8: Leaf Area Index of *Ailanthus altissima* MILL.

	Mother trees	Juvenile trees	Saplings
Tyre	-	4.6	8.2
Chekka	-	20	5.2
Ras Beirut	-	23	4.7
Kantari	61.6	21.7	4.7
Cornich El Mazra'a	59.5	23	3
Sahel Alma	-	23	3.5
Kehaleh	-	20	7.8
Bekfaya	52.3	17.8	4.7
Jdeita	44.3	8.2	4.7
Bhamdoun	46	8.2	4.7

Leaf Area Index of mother trees was the lowest with $44.3 \text{ m}^2\text{m}^{-2}$ in Jdeita and the highest with $61.6 \text{ m}^2\text{m}^{-2}$ in Kantari.

Leaf Area Index of juvenile trees was the lowest with $4.6 \text{ m}^2\text{m}^{-2}$ in Tyre and the highest with $23 \text{ m}^2\text{m}^{-2}$ in Ras Beirut.

Leaf Area Index of saplings was the lowest with $3 \text{ m}^2\text{m}^{-2}$ in Corniche El Mazra'a and the highest with $8.2 \text{ m}^2\text{m}^{-2}$ in Tyre.

Over all the studied sites, the average Leaf Area Index of mother trees was $52.74 \text{ m}^2\text{m}^{-2}$, $16.95 \text{ m}^2\text{m}^{-2}$ for juvenile trees and $5.12 \text{ m}^2\text{m}^{-2}$ for saplings whereas a maximum value of Leaf Area Index varies between $4.1\text{-}4.5 \text{ m}^2\text{m}^{-2}$ has been reported by Gratani and Crescente, 2000. In their study on several Mediterranean species (adult trees) such as *Quercus ilex*, *Pistacia lentiscus*, *Erica arborea*, *Phillyrea latifolia* ... The high Leaf Area Index value of *Ailanthus altissima* MILL shows a significant impact on the companion species and ecosystem by competing them on several physiological processes (photosynthesis, transpiration, evapotranspiration).

3.1.8. Germination Test and Seed Weight

A seed germination test was assessed over 25 days from the start of the experiment, in May, 2016. During the 25 days, the number of germinated seeds were counted (figure 16).

Figure 16: Different phases in *Ailanthus altissima* MILL. seed germination, photo by M.Abdallah, 1/6/2016.

The graph below shows maximum temperature (°C) fluctuation during the 25 days.

Figure 17: Maximum temperature (°C) fluctuation during the 25 days.

The graph below shows germination test of *Ailanthus altissima* MILL. seeds (%) collected from 4 different sites during 25 days.

Figure 18: Germination rate of *Ailanthus altissima* MILL. seeds (%) collected from 4 different sites during 25 days.

First germination occurred on day 10 from seeds collected from Kehaleh with an average temperature of 25.3°C (Min: 20.4°C; Max: 30.1°C). On day 14, all seeds collected from all sites sprouted, with 3 % from Ras Beirut, 3 % from Dekweneh, 1 % from Jounieh and with an increasing from 2 % to 30 % in Kehaleh with an average temperature of 24.5 °C (Min: 19.7 °C; Max: 29.2 °C). Day number 20, after a heat wave with temperature raising to 38.1°C (day 19), the seedlings reached 50% of germination. And in a surprising rate, all seeds germinated to 100% rate on day 25 (figure 19).

Figure 19: *Ailanthus altissima* MILL. seeds germinated at rate of 100% on the 25th day, photo by M. Abdallah, 10/6/2016.

The total degree days to reach 50% germination is 603.7 degree days. So strangely the seeds take relatively long time to germinate nevertheless they are able to reach 100% germination, whereas germination tests on several native species such *Juniperus excelsa* shows a 20-40% germination, *Pinus pinea* L. 70-90%, *Arbutus andrachne* L. 20-40%, *Rosa canina* L. 30-50% (Lebanese Reforestation Initiative, 2011).

In order to be accurate regarding the surprising results of the germination rate, the germination test was repeated twice with a time interval of 4 weeks. The results were almost similar (98-100%). A 100 % germination success rate was acquired in this experiment where information on germination rates varies broadly in literature.

Direct sowing of seeds extracted from samaras in November yielded a germination rate of 98% at a constant temperature of 25 °C (Bory and Clair- Maczulajtys, 1991). Seeds collected in December germinated at rates of 86% and 83% in March and May, respectively, but only 64% germinated in September (Singh *et al.*, 1992). Little, 1974, reported a germination rate of 75% after 1 year of storage.

We notice here that most of the references are reporting very high germination rates for a wild species. Usually such high germination ratio are obtained with selected improved varieties. So without any improvement or artificial intervention the species is giving an absolute high germination rate supporting its invasive potential and risk. Moreover since the seeds are samaras type subject to wind dispersal effect, and the adult trees are relatively high so the spread radius around adult trees is increased and the infected or colonized area around the mother sites is potentially increased.

- **Seed Weight**

The mean seed weight of 100 seeds of *A. altissima* MILL. was 3.725 ± 0.307 g with 4.15 g of 100 seeds collected from Ras Beirut in 16/5/2016, 3.44 g from Dekweneh (11/5/2016), 3.73 g from Kehaleh (16/5/2016) and 3.58 g from Jounieh (25/12/2015).

3.2. *Oxalis pes-caprae* L.

3.2.1. Distribution in Lebanon

The survey shows that, other than the coastal strip, this species was found in regions up to 1077 m altitude (Bhamdoun). It was also found in the Beka'a valley with an altitude of 940 m near Shtoura (Zebdol). The figure below shows the distribution of *Oxalis pes-caprae* L. in Lebanon.

Figure 20: *Oxalis pes-caprae* L. distribution in Lebanon, highlighted in red.

Our results on *Oxalis* as compared to Mouterde and later to Tohmé and Tohmé, are showing clear shift or extension of its area of distribution towards higher altitudes under Mediterranean slopes and more continental weather (Beka'a), this can be explained by either climate change making higher altitudes with milder suitable climate or an adaptation of the species to colder climate since it is advancing from Africa to our regions in the last decades.

3.2.2. Life Cycle

Based on the monitored site (Beblich), *Oxalis* start sprouting in November 2015, as shown in figure 21. The Vegetative growth period extended from November 2015 till the 3rd week of January 2016.

Flowering stage started the 1st week of February until mid-April with an observation of yellow leaves. As soon as the yellow leaves were noticed, the plot was dug up where the formation of bulbs was witnessed.

Its starting life cycle is related to the first significant fall rains in November, later in the winter in coastal areas the mild weather is allowing a continuous vegetative growth and consequently an early blooming in February witnessed in the coastal sites. The blooming phase was cut mid-April due to the end of the rainy season and the start of the biological drought period. While in high elevations, the relatively colder winter is reducing its vegetative growth by delaying its blooming to mid-March while the prolonged spring phase is extending the blooming phase till mid-June. In cold months, significant frost damage is noticed on the leaves reducing the flowering potential and affecting the bulbs production. It should be confirmed in further studies.

Figure 21: *Oxalis pes-caprae* L., sprouting, photo by M.Abdallah, Beblieh, 15/11/2015.

3.2.3. Density

Table number 9 shows the *Oxalis pes caprae* L. density from the 13 chosen sites (the order of the regions in the table below is based on the altitude from low to high).

Table 9: *Oxalis pes-caprae* L. density parameters.

	Total Plants	<i>Oxalis</i>	Other Species	% of <i>Oxalis</i> Plants	% of Other Species
Ain El Remeneh	228	216	12	94.7	5.3
Gallery Sema'an	168	44	124	26.2	73.8
Daher El Ein	958	664	294	69.3	30.7
Beblich	890	526	364	59.1	40.9
Leba'a	448	244	204	54.5	45.5
Nabatieh	310	266	44	85.8	14.2
Kahaleh	752	474	278	63.0	37.0
Bet Chabeb	428	394	34	92.1	7.9
Berj El Mlouk	136	108	28	79.4	20.6
Qrain	120	112	8	93.3	6.7
Salima	470	388	82	82.6	17.4
Zebdol	200	150	50	75.0	25.0
Dhour El Abedyeh	156	152	4	97.4	2.6

Density of total plants was the lowest with 120 plants in Qrain and the highest with 958 plants in Daher El Ein.

Density of *Oxalis* was the lowest with 44 in Gallery Sema'an and the highest with 664 plants in Daher El Ein. The density was related to the landuse or human disturbance more than to natural factors. The density was higher in sites subjected to cultivation than to abandoned lands such shrubby or forest lands. In fact, it could be related to plowing and the addition of fertilizers. It seems that fall plowing is eliminating other plant species, leaving the field free for oxalis competition. Further studies could clarify this pattern.

Density of other species was the lowest with 4 plants in Qrain and the highest with 364 plants in Beblieh.

Over all the 13 sites, the plots shows an average of 424 individuals of different species. *Oxalis* forms 70% of the total individual number and the other species form 30%.

3.2.4. Growth:

- **Leaves and petioles**

Table number 10 shows the shows the morphological characteristics of leaves and petioles of *Oxalis pes-caprae* L. from the 13 chosen sites (the order of the regions in the table below is based on the altitude from low to high).

Table 10: Morphological characteristics of *Oxalis pes-caprae* L. leaves and petioles.

	Number of Leaves			Length of the longest			Leaves' fresh weight			Leaves' dry weight			Petioles' fresh			Petioles' dry weight		
				Leaf (cm)			(g)			(g)			weight (g)			(g)		
	Mean ± SE	Min	Max	Mean ± SE	Min	Max	Mean ± SE	Min	Max	Mean ± SE	Min	Max	Mean ± SE	Min	Max	Mean ± SE	Min	Max
Ain El Remeneh	22 ± 1.2	8	56	17.53 ± 0.6	11	25	0.69 ± 0.03	0.38	0.93	0.08 ± 0.005	0.04	0.16	1.16 ± 0.04	0.69	1.44	0.06 ± 0.004	0.04	0.1
Gallery Sema'an	20 ± 1.4	5	50	13.77 ± 0.6	7.5	20	0.60 ± 0.03	0.5	0.8	0.08 ± 0.003	0.06	0.13	1.42 ± 0.04	1	1.8	0.10 ± 0.006	0.06	0.17
Daher El Ein	11 ± 0.4	5	17	13.75 ± 0.6	9	22	0.88 ± 0.04	0.6	1.19	0.10 ± 0.004	0.07	0.15	0.98 ± 0.05	0.4	1.5	0.09 ± 0.003	0.07	0.14
Beblich	11 ± 0.4	6	22	14.15 ± 0.5	8	20	0.60 ± 0.02	0.46	0.75	0.06 ± 0.001	0.05	0.07	0.60 ± 0.07	0.5	0.6	0.04 ± 0.001	0.03	0.05
Leba'a	25 ± 2.5	5	68	8.05 ± 0.5	3	13.6	0.54 ± 0.02	0.39	0.72	0.04 ± 0.002	0.03	0.07	0.63 ± 0.02	0.4	0.85	0.04 ± 0.001	0.03	0.05
Nabatieh	11 ± 0.5	5	20	21.44 ± 1.2	12	33	0.90 ± 0.04	0.71	1.35	0.15 ± 0.03	0.06	0.7	2.14 ± 0.14	1	3.56	0.14 ± 0.008	0.07	0.23
Kehaleh	19 ± 5.4	7	36	17.25 ± 4.1	11	24	0.65 ± 0.04	0.43	1.2	0.08 ± 0.004	0.05	0.13	0.84 ± 0.08	0.43	1.56	0.06 ± 0.005	0.02	0.11
Bet Chabeb	15 ± 1.1	4	28	10.51 ± 0.5	6	17	0.64 ± 0.04	0.29	0.93	0.05 ± 0.001	0.05	0.07	0.43 ± 0.02	0.24	0.64	0.03 ± 0.001	0.03	0.05
Berj El Mlouk	23 ± 1.8	7	64	13.57 ± 0.4	9	20	0.61 ± 0.04	0.4	1.08	0.03 ± 0.004	0.01	0.09	0.68 ± 0.04	0.43	1.18	0.04 ± 0.006	0.01	0.11
Qrain	15 ± 1.2	4	41	14.98 ± 0.8	7	24	0.52 ± 0.02	0.38	0.7	0.06 ± 0.005	0.02	0.12	0.755 ± 0.03	0.48	1.01	0.06 ± 0.004	0.03	0.11
Salima	21 ± 2.8	7	93	18.11 ± 1.1	7	27	0.45 ± 0.03	0.26	0.7	0.05 ± 0.002	0.03	0.07	0.39 ± 0.01	0.22	0.6	0.04 ± 0.002	0.03	0.08
Zebdol	17 ± 1.4	3	46	12.01 ± 0.3	7	16	0.46 ± 0.04	0.26	0.85	0.04 ± 0.007	0.01	0.13	0.80 ± 0.17	0.28	4.09	0.07 ± 0.01	0.02	0.22
Dhour El Abedyeh	11 ± 1.2	3	43	12.40 ± 0.4	7	17	0.31 ± 0.03	0.13	0.52	0.04 ± 0.004	0.01	0.1	0.53 ± 0.04	0.23	1.1	0.05 ± 0.004	0.02	0.11

SE: Standard Error / Min: Minimum /Max: Maximum

Number of leaves was counted on 15 plants (* 3 replications).

Length of the longest leaf (cm) was measured on 3 leaves from 3 plants (* 3 replications).

Fresh and dry weight of leaves and petioles were weighted for 5 leaves from 5 plants (* 3 replications).

- **Number of leaves per plant**

Number of Leaves per plant ranges from 11 ± 0.4 in Daher El Ein and Beblieh to 25 ± 2.5 in Leba'a with a minimum of 3 leaves in Dhour El Abedye and Zebdol, and a maximum of 93 leaves in Salima.

- **Length of the longest leaf**

This parameter ranges from 8.05 ± 0.5 cm in Leba'a to 21.44 ± 1.2 cm in Nabatieh with a minimum of 3 cm observed in Leba'a and a maximum of 33 cm observed in Nabatieh. In a similar study, Bogdanovič *et al.*, 2002, on *Oxalis* in Croatia reported similar stems length ranging from 10 to 20 cm.

- **Leaves' fresh and dry weight**

The fresh weight of leaves ranges from 0.31 ± 0.03 g in Dhour El Abedyeh to 0.9 ± 0.04 g in Nabatieh with a minimum of 0.13 g observed in Dhour El Abedyeh and a maximum of 1.35 g observed in Nabatieh.

The dry weight of leaves ranges from 0.03 ± 0.0004 g in Berj El Mlouk to 0.15 ± 0.03 g in Nabatieh with a minimum of 0.01 g observed in Berj El Mlouk and a maximum of 0.7 g observed in Nabatieh.

Over all the 13 sites, water forms approximately 90% of the leaves fresh weight.

- **Petioles' fresh and dry weight**

The fresh weight of petioles ranges from 0.39 ± 0.01 g in Salima to 2.14 ± 0.14 g in with a minimum of 0.22 g observed in Salima and a maximum of 4.09 g observed in Zebdol.

The dry weight of petioles ranges from 0.03 ± 0.001 g in Bet Chabeb to 0.14 ± 0.008 g in Nabatieh with a minimum of 0.01 g observed in Berj El Mlouk and a maximum of 0.23 g observed in Nabatieh.

Over all the 13 sites, water forms approximately 93% of the fresh weight of petioles.

- **Peduncles and pedicels**

Table number 11 shows the morphological characteristics of the peduncles and pedicels of *Oxalis pes-caprae* L. from 13 chosen sites (the order of the regions in the table below is based on the altitude from low to high).

Table 11: Morphological characteristics of *Oxalis pes-caprae* L. peduncles and pedicels.

	Number of peduncles per plant			Length of peduncle (cm)			Number of flower per peduncle			Length of pedicel (cm)			Peduncles' fresh weight (g)			Peduncles' dry weight (g)		
	Mean ± SE	Min	Max	Mean ± SE	Min	Max	Mean ± SE	Min	Max	Mean ± SE	Min	Max	Mean ± SE	Min	Max	Mean ± SE	Min	Max
Ain El Remeneh	10 ± 0.7	3	34	26 ± 1.3	16.5	37	11 ± 1.2	2	25	1.2 ± 0.09	0.3	1.8	9.3 ± 0.5	4.8	12.01	0.6 ± 0.05	0.2	0.9
Gallery Sema'an	10 ± 1.7	1	43	24.5 ± 1.4	10	35	14 ± 1.2	4	30	1.1 ± 0.07	0.4	1.8	7.3 ± 0.4	2.9	9.7	0.4 ± 0.02	0.16	0.65
Daher El Ein	6 ± 1.1	2	12	25.4 ± 0.7	19	33	6 ± 0.5	2	13	1.7 ± 0.02	1.6	2	5.4 ± 0.3	2.5	6.9	0.3 ± 0.02	0.1	0.5
Beblich	5 ± 0.6	2	10	20.5 ± 0.7	12	28	13 ± 0.6	6	23	1.3 ± 0.02	1.2	1.6	2.4 ± 0.1	1.7	3.2	0.2 ± 0.01	0.1	0.2
Leba'a	8 ± 1.9	1	35	22.01 ± 0.7	12	28.5	14 ± 0.9	6	28	2.07 ± 0.03	1.6	2.4	3.8 ± 0.1	2.8	4.2	0.2 ± 0.01	0.16	0.33
Nabatieh	5 ± 0.1	2	9	33.6 ± 1.4	16.5	44	20 ± 1.1	8	27	1.4 ± 0.01	1.1	1.7	9.9 ± 0.5	5.3	14.06	0.7 ± 0.05	0.37	1.07
Kehaleh	10 ± 1	3	18	24.2 ± 1.2	15	36	6 ± 0.1	2	14	1.4 ± 0.1	0.2	2.1	4.1 ± 0.2	2.7	6.7	0.3 ± 0.01	0.2	0.4
Bet Chabeb	7 ± 1.9	0	14	19.3 ± 0.4	14	24	11 ± 1	2	29	1.2 ± 0.05	0.9	2	3.8 ± 0.1	2.2	4.7	0.2 ± 0.01	0.18	0.42
Berj El Mlouk	13 ± 0.7	3	32	21.3 ± 1.2	7	31	11 ± 0.5	5	18	1.9 ± 0.06	1.2	2.4	4.2 ± 0.3	2.1	7.3	0.2 ± 0.02	0.1	0.48
Qrain	5 ± 0.9	0	17	21.6 ± 1.05	3.7	30	11 ± 0.6	3	16	1.3 ± 0.06	0.7	1.9	4.6 ± 0.4	1.7	8.7	0.3 ± 0.03	0.08	0.5
Salima	10 ± 0.9	2	61	22.7 ± 0.8	14	31	5 ± 0.4	2	13	1.3 ± 0.07	0.4	1.9	2.7 ± 0.1	1.3	4.4	0.1 ± 0.008	0.1	0.2
Zebdol	6 ± 0.7	0	23	22.07 ± 0.8	13	32	11 ± 0.5	6	21	1.09 ± 0.07	0.2	1.8	3.3 ± 0.2	2.3	4.9	0.2 ± 0.01	0.1	0.3
Dhour El Abedyeh	5 ± 2.2	0	22	20.6 ± 1.1	14	33	10 ± 0.6	2	17	1.3 ± 0.03	1.1	1.6	3.7 ± 0.2	2.6	5.5	0.3 ± 0.02	0.24	0.54

SE: Standard Error / Min: Minimum /Max: Maximum

Number of peduncles per plant was counted on 15 plants (* 3 replications).

Number of flowers per peduncle was counted on 3 peduncles from 3 plants (* 3 replications)

Length of the longest peduncles and length of the longest pedicel (cm) was measured on 3 peduncles from 3 plants (* 3 replications).

Fresh and dry weight of peduncles were weighted for 5 peduncles from 3 plants (* 3 replications).

- **Number of peduncles per plant**

Number of peduncles per plant ranges from 5 ± 0.1 in Nabatieh to 13 ± 0.7 in Berj El Mlouk with a minimum of 0 peduncles per plant (no flowering) observed in Dhour El Abedyeh, Zebdol, Qrain, Bet Chabeb, and a maximum of 61 observed in Salima.

- **Number of flowers per peduncle**

This parameter ranges from 5 ± 0.4 cm in Salima to 20 ± 1.1 cm in Nabatieh with a minimum of 2 cm observed in Dhour El Abedyeh and a maximum of 30 cm observed in Gallery Sema'an. Webb *et al.*, 1988 reported that the number of flowers varies from 3 to 20 on *oxalis* in California.

- **Length of peduncle**

Length of peduncles ranges from 19.3 ± 0.4 cm in Bet Chabeb to 33.6 ± 1.4 cm in Nabatieh with a minimum of 3.7 cm observed in Qrain and a maximum of 44 cm observed in Nabatieh. Webb *et al.*, 1988 reported that the peduncle length is ranging from 10 to 30 cm long.

- **Length of pedicel**

Length of pedicel ranges from 1.09 ± 0.07 cm in Zebdol to 2.07 ± 0.03 cm in Leba'a with a minimum of 0.2 cm observed in Zebdol and a maximum of 2.4 cm observed in Berj El Mlouk.

- **Peduncles' fresh and dry weight**

The fresh weight of peduncles ranges from 2.4 ± 0.1 g in Beblieh to 9.9 ± 0.5 g in Nabatieh with a minimum of 1.3 g observed in Salima and a maximum of 14.06 g observed in Nabatieh.

The dry weight of peduncles ranges from 0.1 ± 0.008 g in Salima to 0.7 ± 0.05 g in Nabatieh with a minimum of 0.08 g observed in Qrain and a maximum of 1.07 g observed in Nabatieh.

Over all the 13 sites, water forms approximately 94% of the fresh weight of peduncles. The high ratio of water in the peduncles associated with the acid content make them consumed as a snack food by children whereas peduncles and leaves are also used in traditional recipes in some villages (Tabbouleh, pies, etc).

- **Bulb**

Figure number 22 shows the number of total bulbs 12 specific sites out of 13 as the remaining site do not have enough individuals to be included in the statistical analysis (the order of the regions in

the table below is based on the altitude from low to high).

Figure 22: Descriptive parameters of *Oxalis pes-caprae* L. bulbs.

Density of total number was the lowest in Leba'a with 272 bulbs and the highest in Ain El Remeneh with 612 bulbs. In Greece, similar studies reported a much higher bulb density of 841 bulbs/m² (Damanakis and Markaki, 1990).

Density of bulbs with less than 0.7 cm was the lowest 96 bulbs in Berj El Mlouk and Kehaleh and the highest with 368 bulbs in Daher El Ein.

Density of bulbs between 0.7 and 1.2 cm was the lowest with 64 bulbs in Beblieh and the highest with 192 bulbs in Ain El Remeneh.

Density of bulbs between with more than 1.2 cm was the lowest with 60 bulbs Salima, Bet Chabeb, Berj El Mlouk, Bet Chabeb and Qrain and the highest with 84 bulbs in Daher El Ein.

Over all the studied sites, an average of 376 bulbs was shown. Whereas bulbs with less than 0.7 cm forms 49%, bulbs between 0.7 and 1.2 cm forms 32% and bulbs with more than 1.2 cm forms 19% of the total bulb number (figure 23).

Roughly 50% of the bulbs are bulbils subject to give new plantlets in the next active season. This shows the potential of invasion.

Figure 23: Average number of bulbils.

- **Bulbs' fresh and dry weight**

Figure number 24 shows Bulbs' fresh and dry weight of bulbs with more than 1.2 cm in 12 specific sites out of 13 as the remaining site do not have enough individuals to be included in the statistical analysis (the order of the regions in the table below is based on the altitude from low to high).

Figure 24: Bulbs' fresh and dry weight.

The fresh weight of bulbs ranges from 3.5 g in Berj El Mlouk to 19.5 g in Gallery Sema'an. The dry weight of bulbs ranges from 1.31 g in Berj El Mlouk to 6.73 g in Gallery Sema'an.

Over all the 12 sites, water forms approximately 65% of the fresh weight of bulbs.

Here we notice a much higher dry biomass content in the bulbs as compared to aerial parts. So the assimilate of the whole plant is concentrated in the bulbs as a storage package that will launch the new shoots in the next favorable season. This is translated later by a fast growing after the next significant rain. This will cover quickly the landscape, and dominate other species.

The competitiveness to annual plants that are starting from seeds in a short day period under colder weather is making the emergence from small seeds slower than the emergence of *Oxalis* from bulbs rich in dry matter. This is making *Oxalis* dominant from the beginning and conducting to the elimination and the reduction of the other plants in the sites. While *Oxalis* shows insignificant competitiveness effect on spring long day's species.

CHAPTER 4: CONCLUSION

CONCLUSION

The present study was conducted as an attempt to characterize two terrestrial invasive plant species in Lebanon, *Ailanthus altissima* MILL. (Tree of Heaven) and *Oxalis pes-caprae* L. (Bermuda buttercup). For this purpose, field survey has been conducted 22 sites covering most of the Lebanese regions where the species are present. Samples and data were collected by establishing plots in different geographical regions.

Concerning *Ailanthus altissima* MILL., this species was sporadically found almost in all the Lebanese territories starting from the coastal strip up to the high mountains and ends up in the Beka'a Valley especially in the central and the northern parts of it. *Ailanthus* grows on a broad range of anthropogenic to natural sites, from walls, cracks of sidewalks, urban parks, railroads to riparian and shrub communities.

Species abundance varied strongly across habitats. Over all the 10 sites, in which the survey was conducted, an average of 26250 individuals/ha was found where 98% were alive and 2 % dead. It was noticed that the studied sites were rich in young trees which show theoretically high invasive potential due to the high density of future mother trees. This species is occurring abundantly due to both efficient sexual reproduction and clonal growth where it grows on a broad range of natural and human-modified soils and also tolerates a broad amplitude of climatic conditions, but seasonal variation in temperature strongly affects survival, growth and spreading. Field observation showed that natural disturbances, such as frost or fire, and human-mediated impacts by cutting, chopping or girdling of stems induce a prolific vegetative regeneration by sprouts that may emerge from the root, the root crown or the stem.

With a rapid stem elongation, *Ailanthus* is believed to be a fast-growing tree, height increment as well as diameter and leaf size growth are highest in saplings and juvenile then in mother trees where it have other reproductive priorities. Upon field observation, an 18-m-high tree produced approximately 120 fruit clusters with a total of 223,200 samaras whereas findings on the germination test shows 100% germination success rate without any improvement or artificial intervention. The species is giving an absolute high germination rate supporting its invasive potential and risk, moreover since the seeds are samaras type, they are subject to wind dispersal effect which the infected

or colonized area around the mother sites will potentially increase. However the high germination rate as shown during our lab experiments is giving in situ a high density of young trees but consequently they will be subject to a high competition pressure, to assure a natural balance by reducing later on the percentage of adult mother trees in the sites.

Ailanthus Leaf Area Index with its high value compared to native Mediterranean species shows a significant impact on the companion species and ecosystem by competing them on several physiological processes (photosynthesis, transpiration, evapotranspiration).

Regarding *Oxalis pes-caprae* L., this species was found in regions up to 1077 m altitude (Bhamdoun) and surprisingly was found in the Beka'a valley in an area with an altitude of 940 m near Shtoura (Zebdol), these are new record as compared to its historical presence in the coastal strip and the low Mediterranean slopes of mount Lebanon. This species occurring in a variety of habitats, it was more abandoned in disturbed and well-drained fertile soil, such as abandoned agricultural fields and orchards, compared with less-disturbed sites such as shrublands and forests.

Over all the 13 sites, in which the survey was conducted, species richness and the relative contribution of plant species shows an average of 424 individuals/m² divided into *Oxalis* and other species, whereas *Oxalis* formed 70% of the total plant number reported. This species was noted to have the highest population in disturbed fertilized areas with sandy clay loam soil. Concerning plant analysis, mean number of leaves, peduncles, flowers per peduncle, fresh and dry weight of leaves, petioles and peduncle were also the highest in disturbed fertilized areas with sandy clay loam soil. Over all the studied sites, an average bulb density of 376 bulbs/m² was observed, with the bulb density decreasing but bulb weight increasing from the soil surface to the depth of 15 cm, however a much higher dry biomass content in the bulbs as compared to aerial parts was noticed. So the assimilate of the whole plant is concentrated in the bulbs as a storage package that will launch the new shoots in the next favorable season dominating the occupied landscape. A notable finding was that *O. pes-caprae* L. stands with more species at the beginning of the vegetative period but became monospecific a few months after germination. Native vegetation, which consisted mainly of annuals seeding in spring and germinating in autumn and some geophytes resprouting from bulbs, was progressively excluded. This indicates that the mechanism by which *O. pes-caprae* L. dominated was rather related with after germination. No secondary vegetation appeared after *O. pes-caprae* L. in the study sites at the year of study.

The appearance of monospecific patches may have significant implications for the structure and function of the whole herbaceous ecosystem.

The result of the present finding indicates that variations in terms of vegetative growth, flowering and biomass of such species are directly related to the abiotic factors that prevail in the identified regions. Climatic factors seem to be a key constraint in defining the limits of its distribution, it was observed that due to its high content of water mainly in the aerial parts, this species doesn't tolerate frost and low temperatures very well, resulting in freeze burn on the areal parts of the plant.

Knowledge and research studies about Invasive Plant Species (IPS) and their threats to biodiversity remain very scarce in Lebanon due to the lack of sufficient specialists in this field and inadequate prioritization at the national level. Yet, IPS represent a real threat, especially to native species ecosystems, and immediate actions needs to be implemented in that regard. As a result, further works should be conducted or to assess the impact of the studied species on the Lebanese biodiversity or to identify the main factors behind the successful invasion of other species.

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Annex-1

List of Terrestrial invasive plant species in Lebanon and the Middle East.

Species	Family	Geographical Origins
<i>Abutilon theophrasti</i> MEDIK.	Malvaceae	P
<i>Achyranthes aspera</i> L.	Amaranthaceae	P
<i>Ailanthus altissima</i> MILL.	Simaroubaceae	China
<i>Alternanthera pungens</i> KUNTH	Amaranthaceae	SA
<i>Amaranthus albus</i> L.	Amaranthaceae	P
<i>Amaranthus blitoides</i> S. WATS.	Amaranthaceae	NA
<i>Amaranthus chlorostachys</i> WILLD.	Amaranthaceae	N
<i>Amaranthus graecizans</i> L.	Amaranthaceae	NA
<i>Amaranthus muricatus</i> GH.LIES ex MOQ.	Amaranthaceae	SA
<i>Amaranthus palmeri</i> S. WATS.	Amaranthaceae	NA
<i>Amaranthus retroflexus</i> L.	Amaranthaceae	NA
<i>Amaranthus spinosus</i> L.	Amaranthaceae	N
<i>Amaranthus viridis</i> L.	Amaranthaceae	
<i>Anacyclus radiatus</i> LOISFEL.	Asteraceae	WM
<i>Anthirrhinum siculum</i> MILL.	Plantaginaceae	WM
<i>Argemone mexicana</i> L.	Papaveraceae	N
<i>Artemisia arborescens</i> L.	Asteraceae	WM
<i>Aster subulatus</i> MICHX.	Asteraceae	NA
<i>Atriplex muelleri</i> BENTH.	Amaranthaceae	A
<i>Atriplex semibaecata</i> R. BR.	Amaranthaceae	A
<i>Bassia brevifolia</i> R. BR.	Amaranthaceae	A
<i>Bassia indica</i> WIGHT	Amaranthaceae	A
<i>Bassia scoparia</i> (L.) SCHRARDER	Amaranthaceae	TA
<i>Bidens pilosa</i> L.	Asteraceae	N
<i>Bromus unioloides</i> KUNTH.	Poaceae	SA
<i>Cenchrus echinatus</i> L.	Poaceae	N
<i>Cenchrus incertus</i> M. A. CURTIS	Poaceae	NA
<i>Chenopodium ambrosioides</i> L.	Amaranthaceae	N
<i>Chloris gayana</i> KUNTH.	Poaceae	P
<i>Chloris virgata</i> Sw.	Poaceae	
<i>Conyza albida</i> WILLD. ex SPRENG.	Asteraceae	SA
<i>Conyza bonariensis</i> (L.) CRONQ.	Asteraceae	SA

<i>Conyza canadensis</i> (L.) CRONQ.	Asteraceae	NA
<i>Cotula anthemoides</i> L.	Asteraceae	P
<i>Cuscuta campestris</i> L.	Euphorbiaceae	NA
<i>Datura innoxia</i> MILL.	Solanaceae	N
<i>Datura stramonium</i> L.	Solanaceae	NA
<i>Dinebra retroflexa</i> (VAHL) PANZ.	Poaceae	P
<i>Eclipta prostrata</i> (L.)	Poaceae	NA
<i>Eleusine indica</i> (L.) GAERDNER.	Poaceae	P
<i>Eucalyptus</i> sp.	Myrtaceae	A
<i>Euphorbia geniculata</i> ORTEGA	Euphorbiaceae	N
<i>Euphorbia hirta</i> L.	Euphorbiaceae	N
<i>Euphorbia nutans</i> LAG.	Euphorbiaceae	NA
<i>Euphorbia prostrata</i> AIT.	Euphorbiaceae	N
<i>Galinsoga parviflora</i> CAV.	Asteraceae	N
<i>Galinsoga ciliata</i> CAV.	Asteraceae	N
<i>Helichrysum luteoalbum</i> L.	Asteraceae	
<i>Helianthus annuus</i> L.	Asteraceae	NA
<i>Heterotheca subaxillaris</i> (LAM.) BRITT. & RUSBY	Asteraceae	NA
<i>Ipomoea cairica</i> (L.) SWEET	Convolvulaceae	P
<i>Ipomoea pes-caprae</i> L.	Convolvulaceae	P.N
<i>Mimosa aculeaticarpa</i> ORTEGA	Fabaceae	Mexico
<i>Mimosa pigra</i> L.	Fabaceae	N
<i>Momordica balsamina</i> L.	Cucurbitaceae	P
<i>Nicotiana glauca</i> GRAHAM	Solanaceae	SA
<i>Oenothera drummondii</i> HOOK.	Onagraceae	NA
<i>Opuntia ficus-indica</i> (L.) MILL.	Cactaceae	SA
<i>Oxalis corniculata</i> L.	Oxalidaceae	SAF
<i>Oxalis pes-caprae</i> L.	Oxalidaceae	SAF
<i>Panicum antidotale</i> RETZ.	Poaceae	In
<i>Panicum capillare</i> L.	Poaceae	NA
<i>Panicum maximum</i> JACQ.	Poaceae	P
<i>Panicum miliaceum</i> L.	Poaceae	In
<i>Paspalum dilatatum</i> POIR.	Poaceae	N
<i>Paspalum paspaloides</i> (MICHX.) SCRIBN.	Poaceae	NA
<i>Phyllanthus rotundifolius</i> KLEIN ex WILLD.	Euphorbiaceae	P

<i>Ricinus communis</i> L.	Euphorbiaceae	P
<i>Senniella spongiosa</i> (MUELL.) AELLEN	Amaranthaceae	A
<i>Solanum cornutum</i> LAM.	Solanaceae	NA
<i>Solanum elaeagnifolium</i> CAR.	Solanaceae	NA
<i>Tagetes minuta</i> L.	Asteraceae	N
<i>Verbesina encelioides</i> (CAV.) BENTH & HOOK. f. ex A. Gray	Asteraceae	NA
<i>Xanthium italicum</i> MORETTI	Asteraceae	N
<i>Xanthium strumarium</i> L.	Asteraceae	N, P
<i>Xanthium spinosum</i> L.	Asteraceae	SA

A: Australia

N: Neotropical (Central and South America) **P:** Paleotropical

In: India (non- tropical area) **NA:** North America (non- tropical area)

SA: South America

SAF: South Africa

TA: Temperate Asia

WM: West Mediterranean

Annex-2

Sites Description:

Ailanthus altissima MILL. Sites

Site 1

Region Name: Tyre

Date of visit: 27/05/2016

Elevation: 11 m

Type of soil: Sandy Loam (Sand: 60.32%; Clay: 8.88%; Silt:30.8%)

pH: 7.4

Water practices: Rainfed

Population: Trees, shrubs, seedlings

Invaded habitats: Archeological site

Plot size: 20 m x 4 m

Number of total trees: 221

Number of dead trees: 0

Number of alive trees: 221

(Mother Trees: 2; Juvenile trees: 57; Saplings: 153).

Site 2

Region Name: Chekka

Date of visit: 01/06/2016

Elevation: 11 m

Type of soil: Sandy Loam (Sand: 60.32%; Clay: 8.88%; Silt:30.8%)

pH: 7.4

Water practices: Rainfed

Population: Trees, shrubs, seedlings

Invaded habitats: Abandoned territory

Plot size: 20 m x 4 m

Number of total trees: 221

Number of dead trees: 0

Number of alive trees: 221

(Mother Trees: 2; Juvenile trees: 57; Saplings: 153).

Site 3

Region Name: Ras Beirut

Date of visit: 22/05/2016

Elevation: 36 m

Type of soil: Loamy Sand (Sand: 84.32%; Clay: 8.88%; Silt:6.88%)

pH: 7.24

Water practices: Rainfed

Population: Trees, shrubs, seedlings

Invaded habitats: Abandoned territory

Plot size: 20 m x 4 m

Number of total trees: 230

Number of dead trees: 1

Number of alive trees: 229

(Mother Trees: 3; Juvenile trees: 68; Saplings: 158).

Site 4

Region Name: Kantari

Date of visit: 24/05/2016

Elevation: 63 m

Type of soil: Loamy Sand (Sand: 82.32%; Clay: 6.88%; Silt:10.8%)

pH: 7.31

Water practices: Rainfed

Population: Trees, shrubs, seedlings

Invaded habitats: Abandoned territory

Plot size: 20 m x 4 m

Number of total trees: 96

Number of dead trees: 0

Number of alive trees: 96

(Mother Trees: 16; Juvenile trees: 27; Saplings: 53).

Site 5

Region Name: Corniche El Mazra'a

Date of visit: 24/05/2016

Elevation: 71 m

Type of soil: Sand (Sand: 92.32%; Clay: 6.88%; Silt:0.8%)

pH: 7.05

Water practices: Rainfed

Population: Trees, shrubs, seedlings

Invaded habitats: Abandoned territory

Plot size: 20 m x 4 m

Number of total trees: 224

Number of dead trees: 0

Number of alive trees: 224

(Mother Trees: 16; Juvenile trees: 63; Saplings: 145).

Site 6

Region Name: Sahel Alma

Date of visit: 30/05/2016

Elevation: 74 m

Type of soil: Loamy Sand (Sand: 84.32%; Clay: 6.88%; Silt:8.8%)

pH: 7.2

Water practices: Rainfed

Population: Trees, shrubs, seedlings

Invaded habitats: Abandoned territory

Plot size: 20 m x 4 m

Number of total trees: 231

Number of dead trees: 0

Number of alive trees: 231

(Mother Trees: 10; Juvenile trees: 93; Saplings: 138).

Site 7

Region Name: Kehaleh

Date of visit: 25/05/2016

Elevation: 525 m

Type of soil: Sandy Loam (Sand: 74.8%; Clay: 6.88%; Silt:18.32%)

pH: 7.26

Water practices: Rainfed

Population: Trees, shrubs, seedlings

Invaded habitats: Abandoned territory

Plot size: 20 m x 4 m

Number of total trees: 229

Number of dead trees: 12

Number of alive trees: 217

(Mother Trees: 10; Juvenile trees: 66; Saplings: 141).

Site 8

Region Name: Bekfaya

Date of visit: 01/06/2016

Elevation: 885 m

Type of soil: Sandy Loam (Sand: 74.32%; Clay: 6.88%; Silt:10.8%)

pH: 7.24

Water practices: Rainfed

Appearance: Trees, shrubs, seedlings

Invaded habitats: Abandoned territory

Plot size: 20 m x 4 m

Number of total trees: 210

Number of dead trees: 2

Number of alive trees: 208

(Mother Trees: 18; Juvenile trees: 66; Saplings: 124).

Site 9

Region Name: Jdeita

Date of visit: 29/05/2016

Elevation: 961 m

Type of soil: Loam (Sand: 44.32%; Clay: 26.88%; Silt:28.8%)

pH: 7.21

Water practices: Rainfed

Population: Trees, shrubs, seedlings

Invaded habitats: Abandoned orchard

Plot size: 20 m x 4 m

Number of total trees: 228

Number of dead trees: 11

Number of alive trees: 217

(Mother Trees: 47; Juvenile trees: 72; Saplings: 100).

Site 10

Region Name: Bhamdoun

Date of visit: 29/05/2016

Elevation: 1077 m

Type of soil: Loam (Sand: 42.32%; Clay: 28.88%; Silt:26.8%)

pH: 7.35

Water practices: Rainfed

Population: Trees, shrubs, seedlings

Invaded habitats: Abandoned territory

Plot size: 20 m x 4 m

Number of total trees: 189

Number of dead trees: 8

Number of alive trees: 181

(Mother Trees: 27; Juvenile trees: 65; Saplings: 89).

Annex-3

Sites Description:

Oxalis pes-caprae L. Sites

Region Name: Ain El Remeneh

Date of visit: 01/02/2016 – 20/04/2016

Elevation: 18 m

Type of soil: Sandy Loam (Sand: 66.32%; Clay: 10.88%;Silt:22.8%)

pH: 7.4

Water practices: Rainfed

Life form: Bulb

Invaded habitats: Sod (no tillage)

Plot size: 0.7 m x 0.7 m

Plot 1: Number of plants: 172 (Number of *Oxalis*: 165; Number of associated plants: 7)

Plot 2: Number of plants: 87 (Number of *Oxalis*: 85; Number of associated plants: 2)

Plot 3: Number of plants: 85 (Number of *Oxalis*: 75; Number of associated plants: 10)

Site 2

Region Name: Gallery Sema'an

Date of visit: 01/02/2016 – 20/04/2016

Elevation: 35 m

Type of soil: Loamy Sand (Sand: 82.32%; Clay: 10.88%;Silt:6.8%)

pH: 7.48

Water practices: Rainfed and irrigation

Life form: Bulb

Invaded habitats: Agricultural land (tillage)

Plot size: 0.7 m x 0.7 m

Plot 1: Number of plants: 38 (Number of *Oxalis*: 16; Number of associated plants: 54)

Plot 2: Number of plants: 102 (Number of *Oxalis*: 35; Number of associated plants: 67)

Plot 3: Number of plants: 84 (Number of *Oxalis*: 17; Number of associated plants: 67)

Site 3

Region Name: Daher El Ein

Date of visit: 24/12/2015 – 19/04/2016

Elevation: 105 m

Type of soil: Sandy Clay Loam (Sand: 79.12%; Clay: 20.88%; Silt: 0%)

pH: 7.21

Water practices: Rainfed and irrigation

Life form: Bulb

Invaded habitats: Citrus orchard (no tillage)

Plot size: 0.7 m x 0.7 m

Plot 1: Number of plants: 545 (Number of *Oxalis*: 262; Number of associated plants: 192)

Plot 2: Number of plants: 614 (Number of *Oxalis*: 529; Number of associated plants: 85)

Plot 3: Number of plants: 369 (Number of *Oxalis*: 205; Number of associated plants: 164)

Site 4

Region Name: Beblieh

Date of visit: 20/12/2016 – 28/04/2016

Elevation: 219 m

Type of soil: Sandy Loam (Sand: 62.32%; Clay: 6.88%;Silt:30.8%)

pH: 6.61

Water practices: Rainfed

Life form: Bulb

Invaded habitats: Olive orchard (tillage)

Plot size: 0.7 m x 0.7 m

Plot 1: Number of plants: 446 (Number of *Oxalis*: 165; Number of associated plants: 281)

Plot 2: Number of plants: 397 (Number of *Oxalis*: 365; Number of associated plants: 32)

Plot 3: Number of plants: 494 (Number of *Oxalis*: 260; Number of associated plants: 234)

Site 5

Region Name: Leba'a

Date of visit: 13/02/2016 – 28/04/2016

Elevation: 370 m

Type of soil: Loam (Sand: 30.32%; Clay: 24.88%; Silt:44.8%)

pH: 7.43

Water practices: Rainfed and irrigation

Life form: Bulb

Invaded habitats: Agricultural land (tillage)

Plot size: 0.7 m x 0.7 m

Plot 1: Number of plants: 230 (Number of *Oxalis*: 20; Number of associated plants: 210)

Plot 2: Number of plants: 237 (Number of *Oxalis*: 184; Number of associated plants: 53)

Plot 3: Number of plants: 205 (Number of *Oxalis*: 162; Number of associated plants: 43)

Site 6

Region Name: Nabatieh

Date of visit: 08/03/2016 – 28/04/2016

Elevation: 427 m

Type of soil: Sandy Clay Loam (Sand: 62.32%; Clay: 28.88%; Silt: 8.8%)

pH: 7.2

Water practices: Rainfed

Life form: Bulb

Invaded habitats: Olive orchards (tillage)

Plot size: 0.7 m x 0.7 m

Plot 1: Number of plants: 210 (Number of *Oxalis*: 210; Number of associated plants: 0)

Plot 2: Number of plants: 153 (Number of *Oxalis*: 102; Number of associated plants: 51)

Plot 3: Number of plants: 104 (Number of *Oxalis*: 87; Number of associated plants: 17)

Site 7

Region Name: Kehaleh

Date of visit: 28/12/2015 – 21/04/2016

Elevation: 525 m

Type of soil: Sandy Loam (Sand: 74.8%; Clay: 6.88%; Silt:18.32%)

pH: 7.26

Water practices: Rainfed

Life form: Bulb

Invaded habitats: Sod (no tillage)

Plot size: 0.7 m x 0.7 m

Plot 1: Number of plants: 530 (Number of *Oxalis*: 355; Number of associated plants: 175)

Plot 2: Number of plants: 247 (Number of *Oxalis*: 182; Number of associated plants: 65)

Plot 3: Number of plants: 353 (Number of *Oxalis*: 175; Number of associated plants: 178)

Site 8

Region Name: Bet Chabeb

Date of visit: 16/02/2016 – 24/04/2016

Elevation: 610 m

Type of soil: Loam (Sand: 66.32%; Clay: 6.88%; Silt:26.8%)

pH: 7.34

Water practices: Rainfed

Life form: Bulb

Invaded habitats: Pine forest (no tillage)

Plot size: 0.7 m x 0.7 m

Plot 1: Number of plants: 196 (Number of *Oxalis*: 187; Number of associated plants: 9)

Plot 2: Number of plants: 386 (Number of *Oxalis*: 380; Number of associated plants: 6)

Plot 3: Number of plants: 62 (Number of *Oxalis*: 25; Number of associated plants: 37)

Site 9

Region Name: Berj El Mlouk

Date of visit: 08/03/2016 – 23/04/2016

Elevation: 617 m

Type of soil: Loamy Sand (Sand: 84.32%; Clay: 6.88%;Silt:8.8%)

pH: 7.23

Water practices: Rainfed

Life form: Bulb

Invaded habitats: Agricultural land (no tillage)

Plot size: 0.7 m x 0.7 m

Plot 1: Number of plants: 87 (Number of *Oxalis*: 84; Number of associated plants: 3)

Plot 2: Number of plants: 55 (Number of *Oxalis*: 53; Number of associated plants: 2)

Plot 3: Number of plants: 62 (Number of *Oxalis*: 25; Number of associated plants: 37)

Site 10

Region Name: Qrain

Date of visit: 09/03/2016 – 19/04/2016

Elevation: 690 m

Type of soil: Sandy Loam (Sand: 62.32%; Clay: 6.88%;Silt:30.8%)

pH: 7.12

Water practices: Rainfed

Life form: Bulb

Invaded habitats: Stone fruit orchard (no tillage)

Plot size: 0.7 m x 0.7 m

Plot 1: Number of plants: 47 (Number of *Oxalis*: 45; Number of associated plants: 2)

Plot 2: Number of plants: 47 (Number of *Oxalis*: 37; Number of associated plants: 10)

Plot 3: Number of plants: 87 (Number of *Oxalis*: 87; Number of associated plants: 0)

Site 11

Region Name: Salima

Date of visit: 31/01/2016 – 23/04/2016

Elevation: 820 m

Type of soil: Sandy Clay Loam (Sand: 62.32%; Clay: 28.88%; Silt: 8.8%)

pH: 7.24

Water practices: Rainfed and irrigation

Life form: Bulb

Invaded habitats: Agricultural land (no tillage)

Plot size: 0.7 m x 0.7 m

Plot 1: Number of plants: 379 (Number of *Oxalis*: 365; Number of associated plants: 14)

Plot 2: Number of plants: 138 (Number of *Oxalis*: 63; Number of associated plants: 75)

Plot 3: Number of plants: 190 (Number of *Oxalis*: 154; Number of associated plants: 36)

Site 12

Region Name: Zebdol

Date of visit: 10/03/2016 – 23/04/2016

Elevation: 940 m

Type of soil: Loamy Sand (Sand: 84.32%; Clay: 6.88%; Silt:8.8%)

pH: 7.39

Water practices: Rainfed

Life form: Bulb

Invaded habitats: Abandoned territory (no tillage)

Plot size: 0.7 m x 0.7 m

Plot 1: Number of plants: 105 (Number of *Oxalis*: 73; Number of associated plants: 32)

Plot 2: Number of plants: 107 (Number of *Oxalis*: 65; Number of associated plants: 43)

Plot 3: Number of plants: 87 (Number of *Oxalis*: 87; Number of associated plants: 0)

Site 13

Region Name: Dhour El Abadyeh

Date of visit: 10/03/2016 – 23/04/2016

Elevation: 977 m

Type of soil: Clay Loam (Sand: 36.32%; Clay: 30.88%; Silt: 32.8%) **pH:** 7.21

Water practices: Rainfed

Life form: Bulb

Invaded habitats: Roadside (no tillage)

Plot size: 0.7 m x 0.7 m

Plot 1: Number of plants: 72 (Number of *Oxalis*: 51; Number of associated plants: 21)

Plot 2: Number of plants: 87 (Number of *Oxalis*: 87; Number of associated plants: 0)

Plot 3: Number of plants: 64 (Number of *Oxalis*: 39; Number of associated plants: 25)